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2 **Mapping Global Live Woody Vegetation Biomass at**
3 **Optimum Spatial Resolutions**
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89 **Abstract**

90 Carbon emissions from forest disturbance are estimated by the area of disturbance
91 multiplied by the emission factors. The area of disturbance is routinely quantified by high-
92 resolution satellite observations, while emission factors are inferred from forest inventory
93 data at national or global scales. This discrepancy between the scale of disturbance and
94 emission factors is hypothesized to introduce large bias in estimates of annual carbon
95 emissions. To test the hypothesis, we used the 30-m global forest cover change to show
96 that on average 80% of disturbances are less than 10-ha in size and 75% of the time occur
97 within 1-km of past disturbances; together pointing to the optimum scale for quantifying
98 emission factors. Using systematic inventory of forest structure from ground, air, and space
99 and satellite imagery, we map global vegetation live biomass at 100-m spatial resolution
100 (1-ha) with a combined model-based and spatial machine learning estimators. We found
101 large spatial heterogeneity of carbon storage at 1-ha scale related to impacts of disturbance
102 and recovery processes and natural edaphic variations amounting to 428 ± 64 PgC (341 ± 51
103 PgC above, 87 ± 13 PgC below) partitioned into 328 PgC in forests and 100 PgC in
104 savannas and shrublands. We verified the hypothesis by showing that there was up to 30%
105 bias from underestimating emissions when the scale of emission factors increased and the
106 bias varied geographically with forest types and disturbance regimes. Our results show
107 that fine-scale mapping of biomass carbon density is essential in reducing the uncertainty
108 of carbon emissions and removals from terrestrial ecosystems.

109 **Introduction**

110 Woody vegetation in terrestrial ecosystems sequester a significant fraction (~29%, or
111 3.1 billion tons in 2019) of the carbon annually released to the atmosphere by
112 anthropogenic activities such as fossil fuel burning and land use change [*Friedlingstein et*
113 *al.*, 2019]. The extent and fate of this terrestrial carbon sink will depend on future climate
114 conditions and human activities [*Schimel et al.*, 2015; *Bonan and Doney*, 2018; *Le Quéré*
115 *et al.*, 2018]. A significant portion of terrestrial carbon uptake is achieved by forests
116 [*Keenan and Williams*, 2018], which cover about 4 billion ha of land surface (~30%), and
117 store about twice as much carbon as the atmosphere [*Sabine et al.*, 2004; *Canadell and*
118 *Raupach*, 2008]. Savanna and shrubland vegetation cover another 2 billion ha in area, and
119 are characterized by mixed trees, shrubs, and grasslands that do not meet the definition of
120 forest (10-30% cover of trees greater than 3-5 height). These nonforest ecosystems have
121 dynamic carbon stocks and fluxes from frequent fire and land use [*van der Werf et al.*,
122 2003; *Turner et al.*, 2018], introducing large interannual variability in global carbon fluxes
123 [*Ahlström et al.*, 2015]. Together, the carbon stored and sequestered in these ecosystems
124 mitigate climate change and provide quantifiable economic benefits for emission
125 reductions from deforestation and degradation (REDD+) [*Gibbs et al.*, 2007; *IPCC*, 2007].
126 Under the Paris Agreement, countries have pledged to develop nationally determined
127 commitments (NDCs) to reduce carbon emissions, enhance removals and participate in the
128 global stocktake every five years [*United Nations*, 2016]. To meet these climate mitigation
129 goals, carbon stocks and fluxes from global forests and nonforests must be quantified and
130 monitored with a consistent and transparent methodology [*Houghton*, 2020; *Harris et al.*,
131 2021].

132 Carbon loss and emissions from vegetation can be quantified by the area of disturbance
133 and the carbon stock before and after the disturbance (i.e. emission factor) [2006, n.d.].
134 Satellite observations at moderate spatial resolutions (30-500 m) have been successful to
135 map the area of disturbance from land use activities and other natural events (winds, fire,
136 insects, droughts, etc.) on an annual basis [Hansen et al., 2013; Li et al., 2018]. In contrast,
137 emission factors used in most studies are primarily from global default values (IPCC, 2006)
138 or at the national level from forest inventory data. This discrepancy between the scale of
139 mapping disturbance and national scale emission factors is hypothesized to introduce large
140 uncertainty and potential bias in estimates of annual emissions [Hurtt et al., 2010]. There
141 are maps of forest live aboveground biomass (AGB) for different regions, periods and at
142 varying spatial resolutions [Saatchi et al., 2011; Santoro et al., 2011; Xu et al., 2017;
143 Ferraz et al., 2018]. However, these maps lack the spatial and temporal consistency to
144 allow reliable annual estimates of global carbon emissions from both forest and nonforest
145 disturbances. Although the maps will be improved more systematically in near future when
146 data from upcoming space observations (i.e. GEDI, NISAR, BIOMASS) become available
147 (Dubayah et al., 2020; Quegan et al., 2019; Yu and Saatchi, 2016), the question of the
148 optimum resolution for mapping global biomass for emission estimation remains
149 unresolved.

150 To address this question and to test the hypothesis about the uncertainty in emissions:
151 first, we developed an estimated optimum mapping unit for AGB from the analyses of
152 satellite derived disturbances and uncertainty of AGB estimates from ground plots of
153 different sizes; second, we mapped live biomass carbon stock at optimum spatial resolution
154 using systematic observations from ground inventory, airborne and spaceborne

155 measurements; and third we quantified the uncertainty of emissions by using emission
156 factors at different scales. As a result of this study, we provide estimates of live biomass
157 carbon stocks (above and below) of global forests and shrublands for the early part of the
158 21st- century (circa 2015). The carbon density map combined with forest clearing and fire
159 disturbance provides new insights into spatial patterns of carbon stocks and fluxes of global
160 woody vegetation.

161 **Materials and Methods**

162 For vegetation disturbance data, we used the Landsat-derived Global Forest Change
163 (GFC) product to identify regions with forest clearing at 30-m resolution (~0.09 ha) from
164 2000 to 2019 (Hansen et al., 2013). While there may be smaller scale forest disturbances
165 across landscapes, GFC is currently the only available systematic annual data product at
166 the global scale. We also included vegetation burned area (BA) estimates at 500 m spatial
167 resolution from MODIS Collection-6 Burned Area (BA) data (product name: MCD64A1
168 v006) [GIGLIO *et al.*, 2018] This is the best moderate resolution data to provide estimates
169 of fire disturbance over all vegetation types globally.

170 The annual Landsat 30-m disturbance data were used in a pixel aggregation approach
171 to estimate the size distribution and occurrence of disturbances in relation to the location
172 of past disturbances. We define the contiguous patch of disturbance with a spatial
173 connectivity approach. Disturbed pixels are considered “connected” when either an edge
174 or corner of one disturbance pixel is in the immediate neighbor of another disturbance
175 pixel. Therefore, two adjoining disturbance pixels are part of the same contiguous area if
176 they are connected along the horizontal, vertical, or diagonal directions. The basic steps for
177 finding connected pixels consists of: (1) searching for the next unlabeled disturbance pixel,

178 (2) using a flood-fill algorithm to label all connected disturbance pixels in the object; and
179 (3) repeating steps 1 and 2 until all connected pixels are labeled. Calculations were
180 performed using Matlab Image Processing toolbox [*Gonzalez et al.*, 2009] for one year of
181 forest disturbance from Landsat GFC at 30 m resolution.

182 For finding the distance of the disturbed pixels of the current and previous years, we
183 first converted the Landsat disturbance map into binary images (disturbed/not-disturbed).
184 Next, we used image binary dilation [*Gonzalez et al.*, 2009] to extend the binary boundary
185 out to 1 and more pixels. Finally, we calculated the intersection of the pixels between
186 binary disturbance map of current year and dilated pixels. The size distribution and
187 distance statistics were developed over $10^\circ \times 10^\circ$ sample areas distributed across global
188 forest biomes.

189 To develop a global biomass map, we compiled over 100,000 inventory plots of
190 vegetation biomass from national and regional networks across all forests but mostly
191 concentrated in the northern temperate regions (**Table S1**). A subset of the inventory data
192 that included tree level information and geolocations were used to develop AGB models
193 from lidar measurements of forest structure specific to vegetation types and ecosystems
194 globally (**Table S1, S2**). The remaining inventory data were used for product validation
195 and uncertainty estimates.

196 Systematic observations of vegetation structure globally were provided by ICESat-1
197 Geoscience Laser Altimeter System (GLAS) lidar (Light Detection and Ranging) from
198 space across all woody vegetation types. GLAS lidar waveforms were the most systematic
199 sampling of global woody vegetation from October 2004 to March 2008, providing
200 approximately ~4.3 million footprints (~0.25 ha) after filtering for cloud, signal strength

201 and slopes. Additionally, more than 1 million ha of airborne laser scanning (ALS) data
202 were acquired across tropical forests at high spatial resolutions (1-m) and were used for
203 local to regional scale biomass mapping [*Xu et al.*, 2017; *Ferraz et al.*, 2018; *Tejada et al.*,
204 2019]. GLAS waveforms were converted to height metrics across different forest types
205 [*Lefsky et al.*, 2007] and were calibrated with ALS data to provide globally consistent and
206 harmonized forest structure for mapping at 1-ha grid cells.

207 We used lidar-biomass allometric models (**Table S2**), divided by continents and
208 biomes, and developed from National Forest Inventory (NFI) in temperate and boreal
209 regions as well as networks of biomass plots across tropical moist [*Gourlet-Fleury et al.*,
210 2004; *Vincent et al.*, 2012; *Longo et al.*, 2016; *Xu et al.*, 2017; *Ferraz et al.*, 2018; *Labriere*
211 *et al.*, 2018; *Meyer et al.*, 2018; 2019] and dry forests and woodlands [*Næsset et al.*, 2016].

212 For mapping height and biomass, we compiled and processed satellite imagery from a
213 combination of optical and radar sensors for the period of circa 2015. We chose the year
214 2015 for mapping AGB to make use of the best quality spatial data from Landsat and ALOS
215 satellites, to allow for integrating a large number of airborne lidar data collected circa 2015
216 (2014-2016) across the tropics, and provide estimates of biomass close to the present time
217 that may be used for national level global stocktake. GLAS lidar samples (2003-2008) were
218 filtered for any changes of landscape from forest clearing to improve the temporal
219 discrepancy between observations of forest structure and the satellite imagery (see
220 supplementary materials).

221 The satellite data includes Advanced Land Observing Satellite's (ALOS) Phased Array
222 type L-band Synthetic Aperture Radar (PALSAR) [*Shimada*, 2010], Landsat 8 Operational
223 Land Imager (OLI) [*Hansen and Loveland*, 2012], Shuttle Radar Topography Mission

224 (SRTM) [Farr *et al.*, 2007], and Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer
225 (MODIS) [Giglio *et al.*, n.d.]. We also used the European Space Agency's GlobCover
226 [Arino *et al.*, 2008] product and World Wildlife Fund's global biome map [Olson *et al.*,
227 2001] as ancillary data to quantify the variations of vegetation carbon stocks across land
228 cover types and biomes (See Supplementary Material). All satellite and spatial data were
229 gridded at the minimum resolution of 100 m x 100 m cells and projected into sinusoidal
230 equal area projection.

231 Estimation of vegetation biomass at mapping grid cells were performed using the
232 modified Maximum Entropy (MaxEnt) [Phillips *et al.*, 2006](Saatchi *et al.* 2011) Machine
233 Learning (ML) algorithm based on a Bayesian estimator to map vegetation height and
234 AGB globally. Data from the training set (~ 5.5 million ha) were divided into bins and
235 ingested into the MaxEnt model to predict the probability of the global distribution of
236 vegetation height and biomass for each bin. The probability estimations for all the bins
237 were then combined to produce continuous height and AGB estimation along with the
238 uncertainty at the pixel level from the Bayesian estimator. This approach was used in
239 Saatchi *et al.* [Saatchi *et al.*, 2011] for the estimation of pan-tropical AGB but further
240 improved by using *a priori* probability distribution for correcting any systematic errors
241 regionally (See Supplementary Material).

242 For savanna woodlands and shrublands where GLAS data were limited, we developed
243 parametric models between the ALOS PALSAR backscatter and ALS estimated AGB (<
244 150 Mg ha⁻¹) to improve the global AGB estimation across small biomass density
245 vegetation [Yu and Saatchi, 2016] (**Table S2**). Belowground biomass (BGB) was
246 estimated from AGB using root-to-shoot ratios for different vegetation types (**Table S2**).

247 For the conversion of biomass to carbon density, we used a default average of 0.5 carbon
248 fraction across all woody vegetation types, allowing users to convert the predictions to
249 carbon using more specific wood carbon concentration factors [*Martin et al.*, 2018].

250 The uncertainties of carbon density estimates are quantified at different scales from
251 pixel level to gridded regional and national levels using error propagation techniques and
252 comparison with national inventory data (See Supplementary Material). We used carbon
253 density and uncertainty at the pixel level along with available disturbance data from forest
254 cover change from Landsat [*Hansen et al.*, 2013] and fire burned area from MODIS
255 (MCD64A1 v006) [*GIGLIO et al.*, 2018] to estimate carbon loss (committed emissions)
256 from disturbance for the year 2016 and quantify the impact of scale of biomass maps on
257 the magnitude and uncertainty of emissions.

258

259 **Results**

260 *Optimum Resolution to Map AGB*

261 Annual forest disturbance size distribution estimated at $10^\circ \times 10^\circ$ sample areas show
262 on average 10-30% of disturbance size may be smaller than 1-ha and varying across regions
263 and forest biomes (**Fig. 1**). In boreal forests, except in eastern Siberia, large scale fires and
264 timber harvests dominate the landscape scale disturbances (>90%). In contrast, temperate
265 forests in southeastern US, central Europe and eastern China have significantly larger
266 number (20-40%) of small size disturbances. Tropical moist and dry forests are mostly
267 dominated by large-scale (> 1-ha) deforestation except in areas dominated by small scale
268 shifting cultivation in Central Africa. The results suggest that the mapping unit of biomass
269 need to be smaller than 1-ha in order to capture variations of forest disturbance size

270 globally. Moreover, new forest disturbances have a higher probability of occurring near
271 past disturbances. There is more than 90% chance that new disturbances occur within 1-
272 km of disturbances of previous years (Fig. 1c). This is an indication that majority of forest
273 disturbances from direct human activity (e.g. deforestation in tropics, forestry management
274 in temperate and boreal regions) are nonrandom events and show a skewed distribution
275 across the landscape. Analysis of distance of burned areas from MODIS 500-m resolution
276 reveals similar patterns of occurrence within the sample areas (Fig. S14). The size
277 distribution of forest disturbances and their nonrandom occurrence across the landscape
278 indicate that biomass needs to be mapped at relatively high spatial resolution to allow
279 accurate estimation of emissions. This resolution also depends on the spatial variability of
280 biomass at the landscape that cannot be determined a priori without mapping.

281

282 *Global Live Biomass Carbon Map*

283 From predictions of above and below ground live vegetation biomass (**Fig. 2**), we
284 estimated the total carbon, stored in about 6 billion hectares of forests and shrublands
285 including all trees and saplings, to be 428 ± 64 PgC from which 341 ± 51 PgC is above and
286 87 ± 13 PgC is below ground. The total carbon is approximately partitioned into 328 PgC
287 in forests and 100 PgC in shrublands, covering all areas of forests, woodlands, semi-arid
288 and arid savanna (mixed trees and shrubs), and coastal swamp forests and mangroves.
289 Spatial variations of AGB for each continent follows a multi-modal distribution impacted
290 by natural variations modulated by human-induced disturbance and recovery processes
291 (**Fig. 2**). South America (SA), with more than 106 PgC, represents the largest reservoir of
292 live vegetation carbon followed by North America (NA), East Asia (EA), and Africa (AF),

293 with similar carbon storage varying between (76-79 PgC). The largest extent of tallest and
294 carbon-dense forests at 1-ha scale also occurs in NA (northwest redwoods) and SA (tropical
295 forests across the Guiana Shield, temperate rainforests in southern Chile) with AGB
296 estimates exceeding 500 Mg ha⁻¹.

297 The prediction uncertainty of AGB at the pixel level (**Fig. 3a**) varies strongly with
298 AGB, showing a moderate uncertainty of less than 50 Mg ha⁻¹ (15-20% of mean) for the
299 mid-range of AGB (50-250 Mg ha⁻¹), but comparatively larger errors for small (< 20 Mg
300 ha⁻¹) and large (> 300 Mg ha⁻¹) AGB values. By introducing *a priori* probability of AGB
301 from available ground, airborne, and satellite lidar data in a Bayesian-based estimation
302 model (See Methods), we were able to significantly reduce the systematic errors in
303 predicting AGB regionally (1° × 1°) (**Fig. 3b**). Comparison of estimates of national level
304 carbon stocks with the 2015 reported numbers by countries with established forest
305 inventory systems (FAO, 2015) (**Fig. 3c**) indicates that the distribution of carbon stocks
306 remains relatively unbiased at large scales. We compared our model estimates against
307 independent airborne lidar derived biomass over the tropical forests of South America,
308 Africa, and Asia (**Fig. 4**). At local scales or pixel levels, we expect larger systematic errors
309 with underestimation particularly for AGB > 400 Mg ha⁻¹ due to the limited sensitivity of
310 the satellite data and lack of reliable training data in the tropics [*Saatchi et al.*, 2011].
311 However, these regions are less widespread globally (~0.66% of areas with woody
312 vegetation) and their contribution to total national or regional carbon stocks is small. To
313 further reduce any local systematic errors in these areas, we adjusted AGB estimates of
314 dense forests using regional airborne lidar derived AGB.

315
316 ***Ecoregion Estimates***

317 We disaggregated the global vegetation carbon into ecoregions [*Olson et al.*, 2001]
318 separated by continents. Humid tropical regions have the largest share of carbon stocks
319 (~175 PgC) (**Fig. 5**). More than 50% of the carbon of global tropical rainforests is in South
320 and Central America (85.5 PgC) with the remaining carbon divided approximately into
321 20% (33.7 PgC) in Africa and 30% (54.2 PgC) in Southeast Asia.

322 The next three important ecoregions (temperate, boreal, and dry tropics) together store
323 about the same amount of carbon in live biomass (~ 187 PgC) as the humid tropics. The
324 total carbon stored in broadleaf/mixed temperate forests are 50 PgC (40.8 PgC in
325 aboveground, 9.7 PgC in belowground), and 25 PgC in conifer temperate forests (20.5 PgC
326 in aboveground, 4.8 PgC in belowground).

327 Boreal ecoregions with 56.2 PgC, (44.6 PgC in aboveground and 11.6 PgC in below
328 ground) contain the second largest amount of carbon. Eurasia contains more than 71% of
329 the carbon (40.4 PgC) and the North America, the remaining 28% (15.7 PgC). This is
330 within the range of estimations from previous studies [*Neigh et al.*, 2013; *Thurner et al.*,
331 2013; *Bradshaw and Warkentin*, 2015], taking into account differences in delineation of
332 the ecoregion boundary, impacts of disturbance and recovery, and potential changes in
333 biomass from climate forcing [*Goetz et al.*, 2007; *Xu*, 2012].

334 Dry tropical ecosystems — including woodlands, dry forests, and savanna dominated
335 by shrublands from sparsely treed landscapes — contain 51 PgC in live woody biomass
336 with 38 PgC in Africa, 10 PgC in South America, and 3 PgC in Australia (**Fig. 5**). With
337 tree cover (10-70%), average height (3-24 m) and live biomass (58 Mg ha⁻¹ on average, 44
338 Mg ha⁻¹ in aboveground and 14 Mg ha⁻¹ belowground), these ecosystems have lower
339 carbon density than humid tropics, but cover significantly larger area of about 379 million

340 ha in South America, 1.2 billion ha in Africa, and 185 million ha in Australia for a total of
341 1.8 billion ha globally.

342 Mangroves at the tropical land-ocean boundary contain approximately 2.37 PgC, most
343 of which is located in Asia and Australia (1.11 PgC), followed by Africa (0.66 PgC) and
344 the Americas (0.56 PgC). These forests cover a narrow band along the coast and both
345 forest height and area are influenced by tidal range, and are thus difficult to capture with
346 coarse resolution maps.

347 *Spatial Variations of AGB*

348 Pixel level spatial variations of live biomass capture the influence of heterogeneity of
349 forest structure at the landscape scale driven by disturbance and recovery process and
350 natural edaphic and topographic variations. We tested the spatial correlation length of
351 AGB in the map using variograms with a size of 1000 pixels across different landscape
352 (see Methods) and found that the variability increases significantly from fragmented areas
353 (range:2-7 km) to dense tropical forests (range: 0.3-1.5 km). The spatial correlation length
354 remained less than 10 pixels (1-km) in each direction for most natural vegetation types.

355 We calculated the heterogeneity of AGB at 1-km² scale (10 x 10 pixels) by mapping
356 the coefficient of variation ($CV = \sigma/\mu$) where σ is the standard deviation and μ is the mean.
357 The spatial variation of CV suggests that globally relatively undisturbed and less
358 fragmented tropical forests are the least variable in AGB ($CV < 0.1$) over large areas (**Fig.**
359 **S3**). In contrast, temperate managed forests and frequently disturbed landscapes in tropics
360 (e.g. across deforested landscapes in South America) have large local variability ($CV > 1$),
361 due to having areas with varying stages of growth from freshly logged to mature forests.
362 A north-south transect across Africa shows the distribution of CV versus AGB (**Fig. S13**)

363 in a gradient of woody vegetation cover from shrublands to woodlands and to humid
364 tropical regions. The variance of AGB across the landscape increases with the
365 anthropogenic and natural disturbance from forest clearing (**Fig. S13b, S13e**) and fire (**Fig.**
366 **S13c, S13f**). Majority of intact and old growth forests with larger AGB values in humid
367 tropics and some temperate forests show smaller variation at the 1-ha scale (**Fig. S3**).

368

369 *Systematic Underestimation of Emissions*

370 By overlaying the map of forest cover change from Landsat data for the year 2016 at
371 the same resolution as AGB [*Hansen et al.*, 2013] and burned area at 500 m resolution
372 from MODIS data, we calculated committed gross emissions spatially (**Fig. S14**) and at
373 the national level (**Fig. S4**). Emissions from fires are considered residual emissions
374 because they include only burned areas that did not overlap with forest clearing (caused by
375 slash and burn) in order to eliminate the probability of double counting. Global emissions
376 from forest clearing and fires were estimated to be 5.8 ± 1.2 PgC, with tropical and
377 subtropical grasslands / savannas / shrublands being the highest followed by tropical and
378 subtropical moist broadleaf forests (Table 1). We found that emissions from forest clearing
379 and fire both show local and regional patterns depending on the extent of disturbance and
380 the emission factors. Forest clearings are mainly concentrated in areas with large biomass
381 in the tropics and across temperate regions (e.g. SE of the US). The residual emission from
382 fire is mostly concentrated in dry woodlands and shrublands across tropical regions with
383 the largest contribution in Africa (**Fig. S14b**).

384

385 We found the resolution of the carbon density map to be critical when calculating
386 emissions. We show this effect by aggregating our 1-ha AGB pixels to larger pixels
387 (100-10000 ha) and applying the mean biomass values to the total area of disturbance for
388 larger grid cells. Percentage of detected emissions at coarser resolutions was calculated
389 using 1-ha scale emissions as reference level (**Fig. 6**). This demonstrates how the use of
390 coarse regional forest biomass values can introduce significant bias in estimating annual
391 emissions from disturbance. The percent of estimated emissions across scales may have
392 nonlinear behavior depending on regional forest cover due to changes of disturbance
393 regimes. The systematic error from the discrepancy between the scale of biomass and the
394 scale of disturbance may become small and show a saturation level for areas of
395 homogenous landscapes where biomass variations as captured by the map are small such
396 as the dense tropical forests (**Fig 6**).

397

398 **Discussion**

399 Estimating carbon loss from disturbance is complex because of two confounding
400 factors. First, the analysis of the Landsat forest cover change products at 30 m spatial
401 resolution reveals that a large number (20-30%) of forest clearings occur at spatial scales
402 smaller than 1-ha globally (**Fig. 1 top**). Second, the spatial distribution of the disturbances
403 is always skewed towards areas of past disturbance because of higher accessibility, or other
404 land use social and economic dynamics (**Fig. 1 bottom**). Therefore, forest disturbance is
405 not randomly distributed across the landscape and hence carbon density of vegetation must
406 be known at the location of disturbance to quantify emission factors.

407 Carbon loss or emission from vegetation disturbance is typically estimated by
408 multiplying the area of disturbance by the emission factor, which is defined as the
409 difference between the carbon stocks before and after the disturbance [*Penman et al.*,
410 2003]. Emission factors are often calculated at the national or regional level from ground
411 inventory estimates of carbon and vegetation disturbance [*Houghton et al.*, 2018]. [*van der*
412 *Werf et al.*, 2017]. However, we show that due to the non-random nature of forest
413 disturbances, this leads to underestimation of carbon loss as we have shown here.

414 The underestimation of the carbon loss from forest clearing using average carbon
415 density of larger grid cells (**Fig. 6**) may become significantly larger when using average
416 carbon density or emission factors at the regional or national scales. This underestimation
417 is on the total committed emissions, irrespective of the time frame of the emission, which
418 is unknown without more detailed knowledge of the disturbance.

419 Mapping AGB at smaller grid cells (10-30 m) in order to capture small disturbances
420 may introduce additional uncertainty for two reasons: 1. grid cells or resolution of the map
421 must be equal or larger than spatial correlation length of vegetation biomass [*Saatchi et al.*,
422 2011]. Pixels > 1-ha better represent the positive spatial autocorrelation of AGB at
423 landscape scales and particularly in areas with greater topographic heterogeneity [*Réjou-*
424 *Méchain et al.*, 2014]; 2. estimation of AGB of smaller plots or grid cells (< 1.0 ha),
425 particularly in tropical and broadleaf forests has larger uncertainty attributed to the
426 application of allometric models to smaller number of trees [*Chave et al.*, 2004].
427 Calibration of remote sensing pixels at 10-30 m with plots of the same size will introduce
428 larger uncertainty in prediction of AGB due to cascading errors of geolocation, noise in
429 single pixel remote sensing data, model error linking remote sensing to ground plots, and

430 errors associated with allometry. Therefore, 100m resolution for mapping AGB is an
431 optimum scale for both predicting biomass and having the least bias in estimating
432 emissions.

433 Smaller scale disturbances, such as a small number of trees being removed from
434 selective logging, would not be captured if the disturbance is not captured by the 30m
435 Landsat product. However, if the disturbance accounts for a large percentage of the
436 biomass within the pixel (largest trees dominate total biomass), it may be captured by time
437 series products of biomass.

438 Our estimates of carbon stocks of woody vegetation improves on existing estimates by
439 (i) including the most recent and systematic inventories from ground, air, and satellite in
440 developing the biomass estimator (**Fig. S2; Table S1**); (ii) using an extensive set of models
441 based on regional variations of forest types to convert space observations of structure to
442 live AGB (**Table S2**), and (iii) developing uncertainty estimates of carbon stocks and
443 emissions at the pixel and regional scales, and (iv) reducing any regional systematic errors
444 in the carbon map. In developing the uncertainty estimator, we made three assumptions:
445 1) errors associated with the ground-estimated AGB and BGB of plot data used for training
446 the remote sensing models are negligible (see Methods), 2) lidar measurement errors are
447 negligible across all landscapes, and 3) errors from lidar measurements, lidar-biomass
448 models, and maximum entropy predictions are independent [Xu *et al.*, 2017]. Pixel-level
449 uncertainty and particularly systematic error will increase if any of the assumptions are not
450 valid. For regional estimates at the coarser resolution or national level (**Table S3**), we
451 included the uncertainty associated with models developed for each ecoregion and
452 accounted for the spatial correlation of the map.

453 Current maps largely agree at regional or national levels while differing on local or
454 pixel levels [Mitchard *et al.*, 2013]. Without reliable temporally synchronous
455 measurements for validation, it is impossible to conclude which prediction is closest to the
456 truth at the pixel-level. Instead, we demonstrated our model does not introduce bias at 1-
457 degree scale (Figure 2b) compared to the training data, compared our model estimates at
458 national levels in the temperate regions where reliable inventory data is available (Figure
459 2c), and compared with independent airborne lidar estimates in the tropics (Figure 3). We
460 included a sample comparison of AGB estimates over the Amazon with three previous pan-
461 tropical studies (Figure S11), and pantropical comparison at 1km scale (**Figure S15**).
462 While the overall patterns are similar, we show different spatial patterns in the subtle
463 variations of high AGB densities across the Amazon. Independent airborne lidar estimates
464 of AGB across Brazil show both higher correlation (R^2 of 0.73 versus 0.19-0.56) and lower
465 mean absolute error (42 Mg/ha versus 51-73 Mg/ha) in this region (Figure S12). The
466 comparisons were performed with aggregated mean AGB of lidar transects ranging in area
467 between ~100ha to ~1000ha. This was done to remove any effect of scale due to the
468 previous studies being at 500m - 1km scale.

469 The improvement on previous biomass estimations is likely due to a combination of
470 factors. Our inclusion of large numbers of lidar-biomass models based on plant functional
471 types and across biomes helped improve regional uncertainties compared with more
472 generic selection of models in previous studies. In denser tropical forests, we improved
473 model sensitivity by including L-band radar backscatter in addition to optical remote
474 sensing. We also used field plot data to help our model better capture variations in wood
475 density which can be an important factor for tropical forests [Chave *et al.*, 2014; Mitchard

476 *et al.*, 2014]. The improved sensitivity in high biomass regions is likely responsible for the
477 differences in the subtle patterns of high AGB regions of the Amazon when compared with
478 previous pan-tropical studies (Figure S11).

479 At the pixel level, the random error may be large due to the noise in the remote sensing
480 data (both instrumental noise and noise from environmental factors unrelated to biomass)
481 and limited sensitivity in areas with large forest biomass. However, our product is
482 relatively unbiased at the regional scale and 100 km grid cells (**Fig. 2b**). This is largely
483 due to random errors at the pixel level cancelling out rapidly as the pixels are averaged to
484 coarser resolutions and spatial correlation error becoming negligible [*Xu et al.*, 2017].
485 Furthermore, for regions of smaller biomass density ($< 150 \text{ Mg ha}^{-1}$), dominated by
486 disturbance and recovery processes, the uncertainty of the map was significantly smaller
487 (**Fig. 2a**), indicating its reliability for quantifying carbon loss and gain from disturbance
488 and recovery. For large AGB values (**Fig. 2a**), systematic error was substantially reduced
489 from the use of extensive airborne lidar data as the *a priori* probability density functions
490 for predicting AGB (see supplementary material).

491 The recent sampling of airborne lidar data in the Brazilian Amazon, Central Africa
492 (Gabon and DRC), and Indonesia provided us more than one million hectares of detailed
493 forest structure to address problems with the patterns of biomass distributions across
494 tropics [*Longo et al.*, 2016; *Xu et al.*, 2017; *Ferraz et al.*, 2018; *Labriere et al.*, 2018].
495 Patterns of forest height structure captured by GLAS lidar have been verified with airborne
496 lidar data and height maps from different approaches [*Saatchi et al.*, 2015; *Sawada et al.*,
497 2015; *Xu et al.*, 2017; *Ferraz et al.*, 2018]. However, conversions of height to biomass
498 without taking into account wood density variations introduced large difference in spatial

499 patterns of AGB maps, especially in the Amazon Basin [Mitchard *et al.*, 2013]. Our
500 estimated canopy height at 1-ha grid cells will allow users to readily apply improved
501 models based on local wood density variations to produce new biomass maps.

502 We found old growth forests in Amazonia span a large range in mean canopy height
503 (10-50 m, CI:90%) and carbon density (50-250 MgC/ha; CI: 90%) capturing structural
504 variability of soil, climate, and species composition (**Fig. 1**). The airborne lidar samples
505 provided additional information on forest structure diversity by validating the spatial
506 patterns captured by the GLAS lidar and showing distinct regional patterns within the
507 Amazon basin. AGB of undisturbed forests on the Guiana Shield were on the average 100-
508 200 Mg ha⁻¹ (CI: 90%) higher than the Amazon Basin-wide mean due to a combination of
509 presence of large trees (>40 m) and higher wood density values (> 0.65 g cm⁻³). In contrast,
510 AGB in western and southern Amazonia was on average 100-150 Mgha⁻¹ lower than the
511 Basin-wide mean due to significantly lower wood density of trees (< 0.58 g cm⁻³), and local
512 dominance of bamboos and palms. The map also identified low carbon density forests in
513 Central Amazonia, dominated with wetlands (Varzea and Igapo) and low-stature forests on
514 sandy soils (Campinarana) where the forest height is on average more than 10 meters
515 shorter than the terra firme forests elsewhere while average wood density is close to the
516 Amazon-wide average (~0.6 g cm⁻³).

517 We used satellite imagery from the year 2015 in the spatial estimator to map vegetation
518 height and AGB. The estimator, however, was trained using GLAS lidar from 2004-2008
519 and satellite data from the same period to minimize any discrepancy between the
520 observation of forest structure and the satellite imagery. We assumed that vegetation
521 growth is much smaller than model prediction errors at the pixel level, and is also smaller

522 than changes due to disturbance that have occurred between the time of GLAS lidar
523 observations and the satellite imagery. Once trained, the estimator can be applied to any
524 date of satellite imagery to predict AGB assuming the images are cross-calibrated (see
525 Methods). Lidar biomass models across different ecoregions were developed from plot
526 level or airborne data simulating the GLAS lidar height metrics [*Lefsky, 2010*]. The same
527 approach has been used for the recent GEDI observations [*Patterson et al., 2019*].

528

529 **Conclusion**

530 Our study has two distinct results that substantially improves our assessment of global
531 carbon storage in woody vegetation and changes from disturbances: (i) We show that there
532 is a significant bias of up to 30% underestimation on average in estimates of carbon
533 emissions from land use and environmental disturbances depending on forest types or
534 regions. This bias can only be reduced by quantifying the vegetation biomass at the scale
535 of disturbance. (ii) After mapping the biomass at 1-ha resolution globally, the results
536 suggest that the carbon stored in trees and woody vegetation outside areas defined as forest
537 (30% cover) can be as large as 100 PgC. This large carbon storage is also subject to
538 frequent disturbance and recovery processes from human-induced land use change and
539 wildfires indicating a potential contribution to gross carbon fluxes annually that are often
540 discarded in most greenhouse gas inventory assessments. Although our biomass estimation
541 may have large uncertainty at 1-ha grid cells, mapping biomass at an optimum scale to
542 capture the variations of disturbance provides a framework for future improvements. Data
543 from current and future satellite observations dedicated to global vegetation biomass from
544 NASA's GEDI (Global Ecosystem Dynamic Investigation) and NISAR (NASA-ISRO

545 Synthetic Aperture Radar) and the European Space Agency’s BIOMASS missions provide
546 the capability to further reduce the uncertainty of biomass maps at finer spatial resolutions.

547

548 **Data availability statement**

549 ALOS PALSAR and ALOS2 PALSAR2 global mosaics are available from
550 https://www.eorc.jaxa.jp/ALOS/en/palsar_fnf/fnf_index.htm ; SRTM DEM is available
551 from the LP DAAC: <https://lpdaac.usgs.gov/> ; Landsat reflectance and forest cover loss
552 data can be found at [https://earthenginepartners.appspot.com/science-2013-global-](https://earthenginepartners.appspot.com/science-2013-global-forest/download_v1.3.html)
553 [forest/download_v1.3.html](https://earthenginepartners.appspot.com/science-2013-global-forest/download_v1.3.html) ; GlobCover product can be found at
554 http://due.esrin.esa.int/page_globcover.php ; WWF Biome Map can be found at
555 <https://www.worldwildlife.org/publications/terrestrial-ecoregions-of-the-world> ; ICESat
556 GLAS data can be found at <https://nsidc.org/data/icesat/data.html> ; MODIS burn area
557 product (MCD64A1) can be found at <https://lpdaac.usgs.gov/products/mcd64a1v006/> ;
558 Airborne lidar and field inventory plots are compiled from various publications and are
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Table 1: Estimated committed carbon emissions from global forest disturbance in 2016. Only biomes with total emissions greater than 0.1 PgC are shown. Global forest cover change (GFC) detected by Landsat imagery (30-m resolution) are considered total forest biomass loss and included in the "clearing emissions" column. Fire disturbance detected by MODIS burned area (500-m resolution) and is considered only 30% biomass loss (combustion rate) on average and included in "fire emissions" column. Fire emissions are calculated for burned area pixels that are not overlapped with GFC to avoid double counting.

Biome	Fire Emissions (PgC)	Clearing Emissions (PgC)	Total (PgC)
Tropical & Subtropical Moist Broadleaf	0.295	1.565	1.86
Tropical & Subtropical Dry Broadleaf	0.073	0.066	0.14
Temperate Broadleaf & Mixed	0.029	0.2	0.23
Temperate Conifer	0.007	0.173	0.18
Boreal/Taiga	0.012	0.291	0.30
Tropical & Subtropical Grasslands, Savannas, and Shrublands	2.636	0.244	2.88

Figure 1. Spatial pattern, size distribution, and occurrence of global forest disturbance. Middle panel: Patterns of forest disturbance showing percent area of forest clearing derived from the Landsat 30 m GFC from 2000-2019 aggregated at 10 km for visualization. Top panel: Disturbance size distribution shown as fraction of total disturbance area that are larger than a given size within a $10^\circ \times 10^\circ$ sampled area across global forest biomes. Bottom panel: Fraction of total disturbance area where new disturbance is within a given distance of past disturbance using the Landsat derived GFC from 2000-2019 for the sampled areas.

Figure 2. Global aboveground live biomass distribution. Histograms show contribution to total continental AGB stock broken down by areas of different AGB density. Continental regions are divided into North America (including Central America and the Caribbean), South America, Europe, Africa, East Asia (including the Middle East), and Australia-Southeast Asia (including Oceania). Geographical coverage is shown in insert.

Figure 3. Spatial uncertainty and validation of global AGB. a) Spatial distribution of model uncertainty at pixel level in units of Mg/ha. b) Comparison of model produced mean AGB at $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ compared with sampled mean AGB directly from GLAS lidar. Coloring shows the number of GLAS shots contained within the $1\text{deg} \times 1\text{deg}$ grid cell. c) Comparison of model predicted national carbon stock with FAO reported values.

Figure 4: Validation of AGB map with independent ALS estimated AGB across tropical forests. Each point on the graph is a lidar track, or patch in the case of wall-to-wall lidar coverage, that is generally between 100ha and 2000 ha in size. One-to-one line (bold black line) is drawn for reference. Areas compared are tropical moist forests located in Gabon and Democratic Republic of Congo for Africa; Kalimantan for Asia; Brazil, Colombia, and French Guiana for South America. The validation is provided in terms of mean absolute error (MAE) in units of Mg/ha and the coefficient of determination (R^2).

Figure 5. Live biomass carbon stocks in global biomes and continents. Carbon stock in aboveground (left bar) and belowground (right bar) pools separated by biomes and continents. Heights of bars are drawn relative to each other by the size of the carbon pool. Belowground carbon is calculated from aboveground carbon using various root:shoot ratios (SI Materials and Methods). Biomes with very small carbon stocks are combined together and shown as “other” with individual values shown in the table insert on the left. Units are in petagrams of carbon (PgC).

Figure 6. Systematic error in estimated emissions from forest cover loss. The percent of detected carbon loss (compared with hectare scale based estimates) from forest cover loss is calculated using down-sampled AGB at coarser resolutions (shown in log-scale to better represent the degree of systematic errors) while keeping area of forest-cover loss information from original 30m forest cover change product the same.

Supplementary Materials for

**Mapping Global Live Woody Vegetation Biomass at
Optimum Spatial Resolutions**

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Materials

ICESat GLAS Data

GLAS lidar can retrieve vegetation vertical structure [Lefsky *et al.*, 2007; Simard *et al.*, 2011; Los *et al.*, 2012]. We used GLAS level 1A waveforms, based on the approach used in [Lefsky, 2010], to derive forest height metric calibrated to ground-based Lorey's height estimates. Lorey's height of a given forest plot is defined as

$$H = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n BA_i h_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n BA_i} \quad (\text{Eq. S1})$$

where H is Lorey's height; BA_i is the basal area (cross-sectional area of a tree trunk at breast height, ~1.3m from ground) of i^{th} tree in the plot; h_i is the height of the i^{th} tree. GLAS shots co-located with field plots and airborne lidar height measurements were used to develop relationships between the lead, trail, and extent of lidar waveform and Lorey's height [Lefsky, 2010]. Separate models were developed for needleleaf, broadleaf, and mixed forests in the form of $H = a + b \cdot \text{extent} + c \cdot \text{lead} + d \cdot \text{trail}$, where lead and trail are the leading edge extent and trailing edge extent of the lidar waveform respectively; extent is the height of the full extent of the waveform from beginning to end of the waveform. The study sites are located in the USA and Brazilian Amazon. Detailed information on the study sites and Lorey's height derivation can be found in [Lefsky *et al.*, 2007]. GLAS lidar shots used in this study covers global woody vegetated areas (**Figure S5**).

Direct calibration of GLAS lidar with ground-estimated AGB is the preferred approach [Saatchi *et al.*, 2011; Healey *et al.*, 2012]. However, due to the potential geolocation error of the GLAS footprint, and the variable footprint size, a direct calibration of the GLAS height metric to AGB is not possible everywhere, particularly in fragmented and sparsely forested areas. In order to quantify the uncertainty in GLAS measurements and the GLAS lidar-biomass models, we first compared the GLAS lidar data with ground measurements and airborne small footprint discrete return lidar (DRL); then we performed the necessary adjustments and estimated the GLAS measurement error. Over tropical forests, we performed GLAS lidar calibration by using coincident DRL data collected over South America, Central Africa, and Southeast Asia (**Figure S6**). A circular footprint with average size of 0.25 ha (56m diameter) was used as a mean effective footprint size for all GLAS lasers. The waveform was converted to GLAS height metric (Lorey's height) using the pseudo waveform derived from small footprint DRL data and compared with GLAS data. For all tropical forests, we used one equation to adjust the GLAS height metric:

$$\begin{aligned} H_{\text{Lorey}} &= 3.21 (H_{\text{GLAS}})^{0.67} \quad (10 \leq H_{\text{GLAS}} \leq 15) \\ H_{\text{Lorey}} &= 3.7325 + 0.96 H_{\text{GLAS}} \quad (15 \leq H_{\text{GLAS}}) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{Eq. S2})$$

where H_{GLAS} is the Lorey's height derived from GLAS waveform, and H_{Lorey} is the adjusted value of Lorey's. This adjustment suggests that the large-footprint GLAS lidar slightly underestimates the maximum height compared to the small footprint DRL data due to the lower signal to noise ratio (smaller proportion of the area of foliage intercepting lidar beam). The adjustment improves the value of GLAS lidar to a more accurate measurement from the DRL data, allowing for developing an improved model between the height metric and forest AGB in the tropics. We did not make adjustments when H_{GLAS} is less than 10m because this generally corresponds to secondary or new growth forests where the adjustment would overestimate the heights of those forests.

Slope underneath the lidar footprint can also introduce errors to the estimation of forest height [Lefsky, 2010]. While slope-correction was performed when estimating Lorey's height, the extent to which this error can be corrected decreases as the slope underlying the lidar footprint increases. To reduce biases that might be introduced by slope, we used SRTM-based slope values to filter out all GLAS shots whose footprint falls over terrain with slope greater than 10%. In total, approximately 7 million GLAS shots from operational periods 3A through 3J, which correspond to October 2004 through March 2008, were processed. Maximum Lorey's Height thresholds are used for individual biomes to remove GLAS shots where Lorey's height is much higher than what would be expected for the given biome. These thresholds are: 15m for tundra; 30m for boreal; 35m for temperate broadleaf/mixed; 30m for shrubland/savanna; 30m for mangroves; 10m for mountain grassland; and 30m for tropical dry broadleaf. Approximately 4.3 million shots remained after all filtering steps.

Field Inventory Data

National inventory data of AGB from the United States and Mexico were included as samples in this study. United States ground inventory plots were provided by the US Forest Inventory and Analysis (FIA) and the Cooperative Alaska Forest Inventory (CAFI) under the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) Forest Service. FIA plot design consists of four circular subplots of 7.3m radius. Trees with diameter at breast height (DBH) of 12.7cm or greater within the subplots were measured [FIA, 2005]. AGB of each measured tree within the plot was predicted using allometric models based on Jenkins models [Jenkins *et al.*, 2003] for the given species and measured DBH. These tree-level AGB values were then summed to obtain a plot-level AGB. Only "single condition" forested plots (2001 and onward) from FIA were included as sample observations (~130,000). These are plots where the entire area of the plot is deemed to be of all one type. Using only single condition plots helped to reduce noise introduced due to heterogeneity within the plot. CAFI plots include a number of sites with permanent sample plots (PSP) located in Alaska [Malone *et al.*, 2009]. Each site consists of three PSPs ~0.04 ha in size. Trees with height greater than 1.4 m and DBH greater than 16 cm within the PSPs were measured and AGB was calculated using Jenkins models. The three PSPs were combined to calculate one plot AGB for each site for a total of 186 sites. Mexico's National Forest Inventory surveyed roughly 2.4 million trees between 2004 and 2012. Sampling site size is roughly 0.04 ha. A total of 339 biomass allometric models were used to predict tree-level biomass, which were then aggregated and extrapolated to 1ha size for roughly 26,000 plot-level AGB measurements [Fernandez *et al.*, 2013].

We collected available research plots from across the tropics spanning various forest types for all continents. These include old growth moist and wet tropical forest, woodland savanna, dry forest, peat swamp forest, and secondary forest recovering from past disturbances. These field plots were included to compliment the GLAS based AGB samples in the tropics. All field plots used are summarized in Table S1.

ALOS PALSAR

ALOS PALSAR, at L-band (1270MHz), provides sensitivity to low to medium biomass density forests and canopy structure of forests [Mitchard *et al.*, 2011; Saatchi *et al.*, 2011;

Yu and Saatchi, 2016]. We used backscatter data from 2007 at the fine beam mode and dual polarizations of HH and HV. The ALOS PALSAR images were processed and corrected for topographical effects at 0.8 arcsec (~25m) spatial resolution by the Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency, JAXA [*Shimada and Ohtaki, 2010*]. We calculated mean value of radar backscatter by projecting each ALOS data pixel onto our model's sinusoidal equal area projection at ~100m pixel size and taking the mean of all pixels whose center falls within the target pixel.

Each ALOS pixel has an associated flag that differentiates between water and land as well as any topographical effects. Target pixels where a mix of land and water pixels were present were marked as either land or water based on majority rule. Only backscatter from land pixels were used in the averaging in the case of mixed land pixel. The ALOS data was ortho-rectified using digital elevation model (DEM) from SRTM [*Shimada and Ohtaki, 2010*]. However, the accuracy of the ortho-rectification is dependent on the quality of the DEM, which is also more problematic in areas of intense topography [*Farr et al., 2007*]. If layover or shadow effects exist for part of the target pixels, those backscatter values were ignored for the calculations. If the entire window had shadow or layover effects, we marked the result pixel as shadow or layover. For shadow and layover areas which are vegetated, we filled in the HH/HV backscatter values for ALOS using values of NDVI based on evaluating vegetated areas without underlying topography.

Landsat OLI

Three bands from Landsat 8 Operational Land Imager (OLI) were used as model inputs: near infrared (band 5, 0.85-0.88 μ m), shortwave infrared (band 6, 1.57-1.65 μ m), and shortwave infrared (band 7, 2.11-2.29 μ m). The Landsat OLI imagery was created using the median observations from a set of growing season observations from 2015, processed by Hansen et al [*Hansen et al., 2013*].

SRTM

We used the global 1-arcsec (~30m) SRTM Digital Elevation Model (DEM) elevation data (NASA JPL version 3) to calculate the mean and standard deviation of elevation at 100m resolution. SRTM used interferometry of C-band synthetic aperture radar (SAR) in a scanning mode (ScanSAR) to create a digital elevation model (DEM) of the Earth with wall-to-wall coverage between 60° north and 56° south [*Farr et al., 2007*]. The NASA JPL version 3 SRTM data filled the voids in the data using Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer (ASTER) Global Digital Elevation Model Version 2 (GDEM2) as well as the USGS Global Multi-resolution Terrain Elevation Data 2010 (GMTED2010) and USGS National Elevation Dataset (NED). ASTER was also used to provide DEM outside areas of coverage of SRTM. We used a 3x3 moving-window to calculate the slope at 1-arcsec resolution. Mean and standard deviation of elevation were used as two separate environment layers for our model. The slope information was used as an auxiliary data for the processing and filtering of GLAS data by finding the underlying slope for each GLAS shot footprint.

Globcover / Biome Map

The European Space Agency's (ESA) GlobCover [*Arino et al., 2008*] land cover product (2005-2006, version 2.2) was used in conjunction with the World Wildlife Fund (WWF)

14-class global biome map [Olson *et al.*, 2001] to provide biome and forest type information. GlobCover product is available at a 300m spatial resolution and separates the surface into 22 different types. Within the 22-type classification, 14 classes are of specific interest for this study as they represent vegetated surfaces with woody vegetation. These include mosaic cropland/vegetation, closed to open broadleaved evergreen or semi-deciduous forest, closed broadleaf deciduous forest, open broadleaf deciduous forest/woodlands, closed needleleaf evergreen forest, open needleleaf deciduous or evergreen forest, closed to open mixed forest, mosaic forest/shrubland/grassland, closed to open shrubland, regularly flooded broadleaf forest, permanently flooded broadleaf forest, and grassland or woody vegetation on regularly flooded or waterlogged soil.

The 14-class WWF map divides the world into 14 biome types. These 14-biome types are further divided into 867 ecoregions. However, we do not have enough field data to take advantage of such a fine segregation of eco-regions. Therefore, we only used the 14-biome types in conjunction with the GlobCover classes to determine the types of allometric equations to apply when converting height data into AGB. Both Globcover and WWF biome maps were up-sampled to the resolution and projection of our model (100m sinusoidal projection) using nearest-neighbor.

Airborne Lidar

Airborne small-footprint lidar measurements over various tropical forests in South America, Africa, and Asia were included as training and/or validation. Small footprint lidar captures canopy-height at individual tree-level. The Canopy Height Models (CHM) were aggregated to 100m then converted to AGB using localized allometries. Measurements in South America include those from intact and degraded forests in the Brazilian Amazon [Longo *et al.*, 2016], Colombia [Meyer *et al.*, 2019], and French Guiana [Gourlet-Fleury *et al.*, 2004; Vincent *et al.*, 2012; Meyer *et al.*, 2018]. Measurements in Africa include those over the Democratic Republic of Congo [Xu *et al.*, 2017] and Gabon [Labriere *et al.*, 2018]. Measurements in Asia are located in Kalimantan, Indonesia [Ferraz *et al.*, 2018]. Airborne lidar measurements over Tanzania [Næsset *et al.*, 2016] were used to develop parametric equation between radar backscatter and AGB for woodlands.

Forest Cover Loss and Fire Maps

The Global Forest Change product [Hansen *et al.*, 2013] and MODIS Burn Area product (MCD64A1) [Giglio *et al.*, n.d.] were used to calculate carbon emissions from forest clearing and particularly from fire as described in a subsequent section. Yearly 30m resolution forest cover loss from the Global Forest Change product for the year 2016 was aggregated to 100m-resolution providing percent forest cover loss map matched with our carbon map product resolution. It is to be noted that the causal agent of forest cover loss is unknown (harvesting, fire, etc.) and furthermore, we cannot presume if this loss is temporary (for example, harvesting or fire followed by regrowth without land use change) or permanent (forest clearing resulting in deforestation). MODIS Burn Area for year 2016 was resampled from 500m using nearest-neighbor to 100m to match the resolution our carbon map product.

Methods

Overall workflow is summarized in Figure S2.

GLAS Lidar biomass allometry

We gathered available ground-based biomass data to compile a list of allometric models to convert Lorey's height to live aboveground biomass (AGB). The relationship between AGB and Lorey's height take on the form of $AGB = \alpha H^\beta + \varepsilon$ where H is Lorey's height, α and β are fitting coefficients and ε is the residual. We developed different Lorey's height - AGB models for different continent/biome combinations (Table S1).

In North America, allometric models were developed using spatial AGB maps based on Canada National Forest Inventory (NFI) [Beaudoin *et al.*, 2014] and US Forest Inventory and Analysis (FIA). For Canada, we developed regional allometric models by randomly selecting a small amount of pixels across the biomass range within each region and developing allometric models between Lorey's height and AGB based on these pixels. Six of Canada's 12 forested ecozones were identified. These correspond to the areas where Canada's National Forest Inventory (NFI) photo-plots are mostly available. These include the ecozones of boreal shield, boreal plains, montane cordillera, boreal cordillera, Pacific maritime, and Atlantic maritime. In the United States, we divided the contiguous 48 states into 5 regions, based on the state division by the US Forest Inventory and Analysis (FIA), consisting of North East, Southern, North Central, Interior West, and Pacific. For each region, we developed an allometric model, using plot data, for each forest type (conifer, deciduous, and mixed), except Pacific and Interior West where not enough plots of mixed type were available. Mexico national inventory data was used to develop allometric models for tropical dry broadleaf and tropical conifer forests. Because only mean canopy height is available from the Mexico national inventory, allometric models between mean canopy height and AGB was developed for these two forest types. We then used co-located plots within North America to find relationship between GLAS-based Lorey's height and ground-measured mean canopy height. This allows us to convert GLAS-based Lorey's height to mean canopy height, and then apply the allometric models to obtain AGB for tropical dry broadleaf and tropical conifer forests.

The boreal forests of Eurasia were divided into east (Russia) and west (outside of Russia) regions. Allometric model for west Eurasian boreal forest is based on plots from Norway [Næsset and Gobakken, 2008]. Eastern Eurasian boreal forest used inventory data from the State Forest Account of Russia [Shvidenko *et al.*, 2007]. Similar to the Mexico national inventory, the Russia national inventory also only have mean canopy height at the plot level. We employed similar techniques to develop an allometric model between mean canopy height and AGB as well as empirical relationship between GLAS Lorey's height and ground-based Lorey's height. These models were then used to predict AGB from GLAS-based Lorey's height. For broadleaf deciduous and mixed forests of China, we used 60 field plots provided by Guoqing Sun.

Tropical forest allometric models were based on numerous research plots spread across South America, Africa, and Southeast Asia [Saatchi *et al.*, 2011]. These research plots span various forest types including old growth tropical moist and wet forest, woodland savanna, dry forest, peat swamp forest, and forests recovering from disturbances. All plots were measured between 1995 and 2005 with a minimum size of 0.1 ha. Trees with DBH > 10cm within the plots were measured. Broadleaf evergreen forest allometry for Australia is based on the Robson Creek 25-ha research plot where all trees with DBH > 10cm are measured [Bradford *et al.*, 2014]. The 25-ha plot is divided into smaller 1-ha plots and then used to develop the allometric model between Lorey's height and AGB. Mangrove allometry is based on 11 plots located in Africa.

Adjustments for AGB were made to account for trees with smaller diameters. When field inventory is conducted, there is typically a lower limit on the size of trees that are measured. In North America (Canada and US national inventories), only trees with DBH greater than 15.5 cm and 12.7 cm, respectively, were measured. In the tropical research plots, only trees with DBH > 10cm were measured. To account for small saplings, we used ratios of 9.8%, 10.6%, and 13.5% of AGB for temperate deciduous, conifers, and mixed forests respectively. These ratios were calculated from FIA phase 3 intensive plots, where trees with DBH < 12.7 cm were also measured. For South America and Africa tropical moist forests, we used $AGB_{sap} = 16.8 - 0.01072AGB$ to calculate AGB of trees with DBH < 10cm. For Southeast Asia and Australia tropical moist forest, we used $AGB_{sap} = 24.263 - 0.034396AGB$.

Geospatial estimator (non-parametric)

Spatial variation of AGB was modeled using the Maximum Entropy model MaxEnt [Phillips and Dudík, 2008] using GLAS based samples supplemented by available ground plot measurements. We used 7 remote sensing image layers (3 Landsat8 reflectance bands: Shortwave Infrared (SWIR) band 6 and 7, and Near Infrared (NIR) band 5; 2 ALOS backscatter: HH/HV, 2 SRTM DEM metrics: elevation and standard deviation of elevation) as environmental layers for spatial predictor variables. Due to high computational and disk storage requirements, a k-fold cross-validation was not feasible. We randomly selected 80% of the sample observations for model input and use the remaining 20% for model evaluation and validation.

We modified the MaxEnt model using a Bayesian approach to estimate continuous variables. For an unknown probability distribution $\pi(i,j)$ at pixel locations (i,j) in a study area, and a set of observations X within the study area, we try to construct $\hat{\pi}(i,j)$ to approximate $\pi(i,j)$. The information from observations X provides the constraints. For the sets of $\hat{\pi}(i,j)$ that satisfy the constraints, maximum entropy theory says that the best choice for $\hat{\pi}(i,j)$ is the one that maximizes the entropy of the probability distribution. The entropy for a probability distribution p is defined as:

$$H(p) \equiv - \sum_{x \in X} p(x) \ln [p(x)] \quad (\text{Eq. S3})$$

We divided AGB into bins and performed MaxEnt probability estimations for each bin. The probabilities for the bins are then combined to form pixel-level estimates according to Eq S4.

$$\langle B_{i,j} \rangle = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^n Pr(B_{min,k} < B_{i,j} < B_{max,k} | A_k)^m Pr(A_k) \bar{B}_k}{\sum_{k=1}^n Pr(B_{min,k} < B_{i,j} < B_{max,k} | A_k)^m Pr(A_k)} \quad (\text{Eq. S4})$$

Here, $\langle B_{i,j} \rangle$ is the expectation value of AGB for pixel (i,j); n is the total number of bins; $\Pr(B_{\min,k} < B_{i,j} < B_{\max,k} | A_k)$ is the MaxEnt estimated probability of the biomass B of a given pixel (i,j) is within the range of the kth bin; \bar{B}_k is the mean biomass of kth bin; $\Pr(A_k)$ is the *a priori* probability of a pixel being in the kth bin; and m is an adjustment factor. We found m=3 to be the best overall choice, as was used in [Saatchi et al., 2011].

The *a priori* probabilities $\Pr(A_k)$ are estimated using the total number of AGB sample units that fall into each bin. This can be interpreted as given an area of interest, if a pixel is randomly chosen, what is the probability of the pixel falling inside bin A_k . The use of *a priori* probability significantly improves overall distribution of model predictions (Figure S7). *A priori* were calculated using a moving window. For each 200km by 200km area, samples within a 1000km by 1000km box centered on the area of interest were used to calculate $\Pr(A_k)$ by counting all samples that fall inside this box. If the surrounding region did not meet a minimum threshold of 10,000 samples, the window was expanded until the threshold is satisfied.

The global land area was divided into six regions by continents to make model computation feasible. Model calculations were carried out in a sinusoidal equal area projection at ~100m resolution -- we used the MODIS sinusoidal projection, but at a factor of 2.5 smaller, resulting in pixel size of 92.7m -- to ensure equal weighting between pixels at different latitudes. Separate models were trained for each region, with the exception of Pacific area containing Hawaii due to lack of enough GLAS shots. The model trained for Southeast Asia was used to make estimations for Hawaii. Although we had separate allometry for mangroves, the number of GLAS shots that fall over mangroves is very low due to the small area, reducing the effect of separate allometry for this biome. We compared our mangrove results with published numbers [Simard et al., 2019] and adjusted our AGB with factors of 1.9, 2, and 1.6 for Africa, Asia, and Australia respectively to correct for regional systematic error.

For mangroves, we used a recent global map of mangrove extent [Giri et al., 2010 version1.3] to estimate the carbon content and mangrove-specific shoot-to-root ratio to adjust for the below ground biomass [Komiyama et al., 2008].

Low biomass parametric estimation (ALOS)

In areas with small biomass values (<150 Mg/ha), such as savannas, woodlands, taiga and tundra, GLAS-samples may be inconsistent as the probability of sampling a sparsely vegetated surface is low. However, these regions are well below the biomass saturation level of L-band backscatter from ALOS [Yu and Saatchi, 2016]. Because our modified MaxEnt model separates AGB into bins of approximately 30 Mg/ha in size, the ability of the model in predicting small AGB values, similar in value to the lowest bin, is also limited. Therefore, areas where model predicted AGB is < 50 Mg/ha was replaced with predictions from parametric models [Yu and Saatchi, 2016] using the HV polarization of ALOS. We also developed a parametric model for tropical savannas and woodlands using biomass data derived from airborne lidar over Tanzania. This model is given as follows where hv is the ALOS backscatter in HV polarization in power units.

$$AGB = 21495 hv^{1.7578} \text{ (Eq. S5)}$$

Belowground biomass

We estimated belowground biomass (BGB) as a function of AGB. The typical way BGB is estimated is through the use of a simple root:shoot ratios [Mokany *et al.*, 2006]. We also used the root:shoot ratio for most vegetation types with a few exceptions where other functional forms provided better fit (Table S2). For Southeast Asia, BGB model was estimated based on available field plots. For US ecoregions, FIA plots within each ecoregion were used to calculate a simple root:shoot ratio for each forest type within that ecoregion. For boreal forests, the mean plot based BGB values were taken from Næsset & Gobakken [Næsset and Gobakken, 2008] and AGB to BGB ratios were estimated from the mean values (Figure S8). For other regions, root:shoot ratios were used based on existing literature [Mokany *et al.*, 2006].

Estimation of Carbon Loss

Carbon loss from forest cover changes was calculated for forest clearing and burned areas. For forest clearing, we resampled Landsat pixels from global forest change (GFC) [Hansen *et al.*, 2013] maps to 100 m resolution by keeping the percent of area cleared for each grid cell. The resampling process was performed by first projecting Landsat grid cells from 0.00025 degrees geographic projection to 25 m in sinusoidal equal area projection and then keeping the percent area of a pixel cleared within 100 m grid cell (4x4 pixels). For burned area we used the MODIS burned area (product name: MCD64A1 v006) product at 500 m resolution. We resampled the biomass map to 500 m resolution to match the grid cells of the burned area to calculate the carbon loss or emissions from fire. For forest clearing we used the emission efficiency factor of 1.0 and for fire an average value of 0.3 [Carvalho *et al.*, 2016]. We calculated an upper and lower bound estimate of carbon emission based on disturbance maps and carbon stock maps using total carbon stocks (above + below) for forest clearing and above ground for forest fire. We used a carbon fraction of 0.5 for all forest types.

For pure forest loss from Landsat, emissions are calculated from multiplying the carbon stocks prior to disturbance by the area of disturbance. For pure fire fire pixels (not overlapped with Landsat forest loss), we performed the same analysis with combustion efficiency of 0.3 for AGB. We then calculated a lower and upper-bound estimate of emissions for all pixels that include overlapped areas. Lower-bound estimation assumes that in pixels where both forest loss has occurred and fire was detected, the entire burn area is captured by forest loss map. Therefore, only forest loss, f_{loss} , is used to calculate emissions. Upper-bound estimation assumes that in pixels where both forest-loss and fire were detected, the fire was not captured by the forest-loss map. In this case, we calculated the proportion of forest clearing within the 500 m grid cells, and estimated emissions from fire from the remaining area of the pixel. For a given pixel, the carbon emission of that pixel was calculated as follows:

$$E_{upper} = \begin{cases} f_{loss} C & \text{loss only} \\ f_{loss} C + 0.3(1 - f_{loss})C & \text{loss + burn} \\ 0.3C & \text{burn only} \end{cases} \quad (\text{Eq. S6})$$

$$E_{lower} = \begin{cases} f_{loss} C & \text{loss only, loss + burn} \\ 0.3C & \text{burn only} \end{cases} \quad (\text{Eq. S7})$$

Here, E_{upper} and E_{lower} are the upper and lower limit emissions respectively. f_{loss} is the fraction of forest cover loss from Landsat. C is the total carbon in the given pixel.

Estimation of national carbon stocks

National inventories of carbon stocks were estimated by first summing up the total live biomass (AGB+BGB), then applying a carbon fraction of 0.5, to estimate total carbon. The definition of forest cover can have an important effect here, and needs to be taken into account carefully when comparing with other estimates. We performed the carbon inventory separating forest and non-forest using the ALOS-based Forest Non-Forest (FNF) mask [Shimada *et al.*, 2014] (Table S2).

Uncertainty analysis

Uncertainty in the final AGB estimation can come from a variety of sources. In the order of our entire model process, the uncertainty can come from ground sample data (measurement and tree-level allometric equations), modeling of Lorey's height from GLAS waveform, allometric models for converting Lorey's height to plot level AGB, geolocation errors of samples, time mismatch between sample and remote sensing layers, and modified MaxEnt model prediction errors. These sources of error can be grouped into measurement error ($\sigma_{\text{measurement}}$), allometric error ($\sigma_{\text{allometry}}$), sampling error (σ_{sampling}), and prediction error ($\sigma_{\text{prediction}}$).

Measurement error ($\sigma_{\text{measurement}}$) contains the error in estimation of Lorey's height from GLAS. The root mean squared error (RMSE) for the GLAS estimation of Lorey's height is 3.3m, 4.9m, and 6.9m for broadleaf, needleleaf, and mixed forests respectively [Lefsky, 2010]. These errors can be converted to relative errors by dividing by the mean Lorey's height of these forest types, giving 13.7%, 20.3%, and 28.6% for broadleaf, needleleaf, and mixed forests respectively. There are also errors associated with ground estimation of Lorey's height from sample selection of trees and DBH and height measurements. We assumed these errors to be small relative to errors from GLAS estimation of Lorey's height.

Allometric error, $\sigma_{\text{allometry}}$, was estimated using bootstrapping of Lorey's height and AGB samples. The 95 and 5 percent confidence intervals of AGB were estimated to be less than $\pm 2\%$ for temperate forests and less than $\pm 10\%$ for tropical forests for AGB ranges greater than 50 Mg/ha. The errors associated with the ground measurements of DBH have been estimated at less than 5% by the US Forest Service [McRoberts *et al.*, 1994] but can vary greatly due to field crew training and vegetation types being measured.

The sampling error (σ_{sampling}) consists of the error associated with the representativeness of GLAS and field plots of the true distribution of the region, and the error associated with the σ_{model} prediction of the biomass distribution of the region. We calculated the latter by analyzing the results in 1 degree blocks and comparing them with the distribution of the GLAS samples.

Prediction error ($\sigma_{\text{prediction}}$) can be quantified in two ways. 1. We used the 20% of the samples that were set aside to calculate the errors at the sample level associated with our model prediction; 2. We calculated the internal model uncertainty by combining the probability produced by the different AGB bins. The use of MaxEnt model also allows us to calculate an internal model uncertainty at the pixel level. We utilize the fact that a probability distribution is generated for the entire area of study for every AGB bin we use. Combining these probabilities produces a pixel-level uncertainty estimate:

$$\sigma_{\hat{B}} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{k=1}^N (B_k - \hat{B})^2 P_k P(A_k)}{\sum_{k=1}^N P_k P(A_k)}} \quad (\text{Eq. S8})$$

where B_k is the mean biomass of the k^{th} range, \hat{B} is the predicted biomass value, P_k is the MaxEnt generated probability for biomass range k , and $P(A_k)$ is the prior probability of any pixel being in biomass range k as used in equation S4. This pixel level uncertainty $\sigma_{\hat{B}}$ increases if the probability for each AGB bin for a given pixel are all relatively similar to each other (meaning the model is not certain in discriminating the pixel as belonging to just one bin), and decreases if one bin is strongly favored over the others. The relative uncertain for each pixel can then be calculated as $\sigma_{prediction} = \frac{\sigma_{\hat{B}}}{\hat{B}} \times 100$.

We can then calculate the total uncertainty in estimating AGB, assuming all errors were independent and random, by using

$$\sigma_{AGB} = \sqrt{\sigma_{measure}^2 + \sigma_{allometry}^2 + \sigma_{sampling}^2 + \sigma_{prediction}^2} \quad (\text{Eq. S9})$$

where each of the terms are the relative errors at that pixel. The uncertainty in BGB can be calculated by propagating Eq. S9 through the equations used for BGB by using

$$\sigma_{BGB} = \sqrt{\sigma_{BGBallometry}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial AGB}\right)^2} \quad (\text{Eq. S10})$$

where $\sigma_{BGBallometry}^2$ is the uncertainty of the AGB to BGB allometric equation, and f is the AGB to BGB model. The total uncertainty of carbon stock at each pixel is therefore given by $\sigma_{\mu}^2 = \sigma_{AGB}^2 + \sigma_{BGB}^2$.

When aggregating pixel model estimates into regional, national, or global estimates, random errors cancel out and become negligible, leaving model parameter errors to dominate [Chen *et al.*, 2016]. The regional scale uncertainty estimation needs considerations of pixel-level covariance of both the modeling uncertainty and the residual term (Xu *et al.*, 2017).

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{\text{MSE}}(\hat{\mu}) &= \frac{1}{N^2} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^N \widehat{\text{Cov}}(\sigma_{\varepsilon,i}, \sigma_{\varepsilon,j}) + \frac{1}{N^2} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^N \widehat{\text{Cov}}(\sigma_{\mu,i}, \sigma_{\mu,j}) \\ &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \widehat{\text{Var}}(\sigma_{\varepsilon}) + \frac{1}{N^2} \sum_{i \neq k}^N \sum_{k=1}^N \widehat{\text{Cov}}(\sigma_{\varepsilon,i}, \sigma_{\varepsilon,j}) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{N^2} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^N \widehat{\text{Cov}}(\sigma_{\mu,i}, \sigma_{\mu,j}) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{Eq.S11})$$

where MSE is the mean squared error of the regional mean estimate of carbon stocks from a total of N pixels. For pixel-level uncertainty, this includes the sources of error related to residual error variance $\sigma_{\varepsilon,i}^2$, prediction error that will include parameter model error variance $\sigma_{\mu,i}^2$ and measurement error from predictor variables $\sigma_{X,i}^2$. Assuming that predictor variables have unknown but negligible errors (as the information is often unavailable for remote sensing data), we have pixel-level uncertainty.

$$\sigma_i^2 = \sigma_{\varepsilon,i}^2 + \sigma_{\mu,i}^2 \quad (\text{Eq. S12})$$

The two covariance terms are sources of errors related to prediction residuals and model parameters. When the sample size of the established model is sufficiently large, the residual

variance and covariance (components related to σ_ε) due to spatial autocorrelation in Eq. S11 are negligible for regional estimates (*Xu et al. 2017*), and the model-related (σ_μ) covariance term, can be readily estimated using bootstrapping procedure to account for both the model parameter uncertainty and the corresponding covariance between pixel predictions. We used the higher end of 95 percentile confidence estimate in allometric model parameter error of $\pm 10\%$ [*Chave et al., 2014*], and added a possible systematic error derived from bootstrapping approach, to arrive at the uncertainty for regional and global estimates of carbon stocks at 95% confidence intervals.

For estimating emissions, other sources of errors may be included in the error propagation model such as the errors in estimating forest cover change from the Landsat GFC product [*Hansen et al., 2013*] and errors associated with the detection of burned area from the MODIS satellite, and the combustion factor. A simple assumption for the error propagation model discussed earlier is their statistical independence.

1-degree evaluation

Evaluation of model performance at the regional scale was performed by dividing the global region into 1-degree by 1-degree grid cells. For each of these grid cells, we gathered all the GLAS shots that fall inside and calculated the mean AGB. We also calculated the model predicted mean AGB for the 1-degree grid cell by averaging all the pixels with a non-zero value of AGB. Non-zero pixel values were used because our GLAS-based AGB dataset only contains non-zero values where the GLAS-shot returns a valid vertical wave-form that can be used to retrieve a non-zero Lorey's height.

Comparison with Airborne-LiDAR

We evaluated the performance of our model in the tropical moist forests by comparing model predicted AGB with available airborne LiDAR derived AGB. Even though airborne lidar has resolution finer than 100m, comparison at our product's pixel level (1-ha) is difficult due to geo-location error and large pixel level prediction uncertainty. Instead, we compared the mean AGB of airborne LiDAR transects, or regions in the case of wall-to-wall LiDAR coverage, with areas ranging between 100ha to 2000ha (Figure S9). South American airborne LiDAR includes data from the Brazilian Amazon [*Longo et al., 2016*], Colombia [*Meyer et al., 2019*], and French Guiana [*Vincent et al., 2012; Meyer et al., 2018*]. Africa includes data from the Democratic Republic of Congo [*Xu et al., 2017*] and Gabon [*Labriere et al., 2018*]. Asia includes LiDAR data from Kalimantan, Indonesia [*Ferraz et al., 2018*]. We used vector shape files to calculate mean AGB from the selected areas from both airborne-LiDAR derived AGB and our model predicted AGB (Figure S9).

Disturbance Scale Analysis

We used a section of the Amazon Basin to analyze typical patterns of forest disturbance. The 30m Landsat derived forest cover and forest loss map [*Hansen et al., 2013*] (Figure S10a) were aggregated using two approaches. The first approach looks at the distribution of contiguous forest clearing at least 90m in size through the use of segmentation (Figure S10b). The second approach looks at the 90m x 90m pixels only where the full 90m pixel is cleared (Figure S10c). This shows that 90m size is able to capture most of the smaller 30m forest clearing due to the fact that most of those 30m disturbances are next to other

disturbances. The non-random feature of forest clearing temporally as well as spatially is also shown in Figure S11. These non-random features suggest that using average biomass of the entire scene from coarse resolution biomass maps will introduce biases into the result.

We tested the effect of the scale of biomass maps on quantification of carbon removal using our 1-ha scale AGB map and 30m Landsat forest cover loss map [*Hansen et al.*, 2013] aggregated to the same resolution as our AGB map. We calculated carbon removal at 1-ha scale by aggregating biomass of the pixels that were cleared. The maps were then aggregated to coarser resolutions using averaging for AGB and calculating percent forest cover loss at the pixel level for forest cover loss map. For coarser resolutions, to calculate carbon removal from a pixel, we used the AGB of the pixel (averaged from finer resolution AGB map, to simulate coarser resolution AGB map that does not have sub-pixel information on how the biomass is distributed within the pixel) multiplied by the percent cover loss of the pixel. The calculations were performed for resolution down to 8000-ha pixel size.

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Fig. S1. Global distribution, by latitude, of (a) area, carbon density, total carbon stocks, and forest inventory plots, and (b) distribution of satellite observations showing woody vegetation cover from MODIS VCF (Vegetation Continuous Field), and systematic vegetation structure samples from GLAS lidar footprints. Values are summed over 1 degree latitude bands. Total forest and shrub areas are calculated using GlobCover. Inventory density reflects current existing ground inventory by using reported national averages.

Fig. S2. Flow chart showing overall structure of methodology.

Fig. S3. Coefficient of variation (CV) of the above ground biomass calculated at the 1-km (100 ha) pixels showing the heterogeneity of biomass from natural variability of vegetation cover and structure due to edaphic conditions and the influence and of disturbance and recovery process. Dotted line in Africa shows the transect used to calculate spatial variation of AGB in Figure S13.

Fig. S4. Carbon emissions from forest clearing and vegetation fire at the national level for the year 2015-2016.

Figure S5. Spatial coverage of all GLAS lidar shots used in this study. Note that we only retain a GLAS shot where a valid Lorey's height can be calculated. This means that the lidar waveform must demonstrate a ground return as well as vegetation vertical structure. Therefore, all the GLAS shots used are over vegetated areas.

Figure S6. Scatter plot of Lorey’s height derived from coincident GLAS shots and airborne lidar tracts. The lidar shots are collected over tropical forests of South America, Central Africa, and Southeast Asia. The fitted line shows an under-estimation by GLAS when compared with small-footprint airborne lidar. This relationship is used to correct for this error in GLAS-derived Lorey’s height for the tropical forests.

Figure S7. Testing of the effect of prior probability in Eq. S4. The test was performed using GLAS-based Lorey's height without applying any allometry. The model is run over the Amazon tropical moist forest with the GLAS-based Lorey's height as input samples. The blue line shows the normalized distribution model output Lorey's height without using the prior probability in Eq. S4. Red line shows the distribution of the same model run using prior probability. Black line shows the distribution of Lorey's height from the GLAS samples.

Figure S8. Relationships between AGB and BGB developed from field plots in boreal forests of Norway(34). We chose 145 Mg/ha AGB as a break point for the function fits as plots above and below this value appear to follow slightly different slopes. For $AGB \leq 145 \text{Mg/ha}$, $BGB = 0.238AGB$. For $AGB > 145 \text{Mg/ha}$, $BGB = 1.7 + 0.215AGB$.

Figure S9. Distribution of the forest clearing (in white) across the landscape in year 2015-2016 using three spatial resolutions, with a) at the 30 m resolution of Landsat detection algorithm (Hansen et al., 2013), b) distribution of contiguous forest clearing with minimum size of about 90 m derived from segmentation approach, and c) distribution of forest clearing at 90 m derived from averaging to capture only fully deforested pixels at 90 x 90 pixels.

Figure S10. Time series of forest clearing in a site within the Amazon Basin showing the patterns of non-random deforestation in space and time, suggesting using average biomass of the entire scene may introduce bias in emissions. Emissions derived from multiplying area of deforestation with the biomass of forest prior to clearing and at the same spatial scale.

Figure S11. Comparison of AGB density over the Amazon rain forest with three previous pan-tropical studies [*Saatchi et al.*, 2011; *Baccini et al.*, 2012; *Avitabile et al.*, 2016].

Figure S12. Validation of AGB density in Brazil using independent airborne lidar estimates [Longo *et al.*, 2016] compared with previous pan-tropical studies [Saatchi *et al.*, 2011; Baccini *et al.*, 2012; Avitabile *et al.*, 2016]. Lidar transects vary in size from ~100ha to ~1000ha (shown as marker color, in units of ha). Mean lidar estimated AGB density is calculated for each transect and compared with mean density of corresponding areas over the biomass maps. Lidar measurements were performed between 2012 and 2015.

Figure S13. Spatial variations of AGB across a north-south transect in central Africa separated by vegetation types along the latitudinal axis showing: a) distribution of AGB in Mg/ha, b) fractions of deforestation derived from the Landsat time series in 2015-2016 period, c) variations fraction of burned area from wildfires in forests and shrublands, d) coefficient of variation of AGB calculated at the 1-km pixels binned in AGB range across the transect showing the mean and variations (shaded grey) of CV, e) variations of fraction of deforested area calculated at 1-km pixels binned in AGB range, and f) variations of fraction of burned area across the transect binned in AGB range.

Figure S14. Spatial distribution of carbon emissions averaged for 2015-2016 period from (a) forest clearing and (b) fire in forests and nonforest areas by removing the overlap areas to eliminate the double counting of emissions.

Figure S15. Comparison of our model prediction with reference AGB estimates at approximately 1km scale [Avitabile *et al.*, 2016]. Points are divided into 20 Mg/ha bins, with the highest bin being >240 Mg/ha due to the small number of points in the higher biomass range. Dots show the means values while the whiskers show the range from the first quartile to the third quartile.

Table S1. Summary of field inventory plots used in this study. Field plots were used for developing allometric models, regional calibration of wood density in the tropics, and regional validation.

Regions / Countries	Vegetation Type	No of Plots / Size	Source
North America			
Canada			
Mexico	Dry and moist	114 (0.1 ha)	Winrock/CONAFOR: https://www.winrock.org
Mexico	Dry	29 (0.1 ha)	Winrock/USAID: https://www.winrock.org
United States	Temperate Evergreen, Deciduous, Mixed	131,619 (0.4 ha)	USDA Forest Service (FIA): Domke, Grant M -FS <grant.m.domke@usda.gov>
Eurasia			
Norway	Boreal	201 (0.02 - 0.04 ha)	Erik Næsset <erik.naesset@nmbu.no>
Russia	Taiga	2797	[<i>Shvidenko et al., 2007</i>] : SHCHEPASHCHENKO Dmitry <schepd@iiasa.ac.at>
Europe	Temperate Evergreen, Deciduous, Mixed, boreal conifers	Jurisdictional Carbon Estimates from 192,785 inventory plots from Norway, Sweden, Netherlands, Germany, Ireland, Poland, France, Spain, Switzerland, Italy, Portugal	[<i>Schelhaas et al., 2018</i>] : Nabuurs, Gert-Jan <gert-jan.nabuurs@wur.nl>: https://www.efi.int/knowledge/models/efiscen/inventory
South & Central America			
Pan Amazon	Moist tropical forests	413 (0.25-2.25 ha)	[<i>Mitchard et al., 2014</i>]
Argentina	primary, secondary forests	56 (0.1 ha)	[<i>Bonino, 2006</i>] Emma Bonino: estelabonino@arnet.com.ar
Belize	Pine grassland and woodland, shrub grassland, pine-oak	187	Winrock/The Nature Conservancy: https://www.winrock.org

	woodland, upland forest, bajo forest, burned forest		
Colombia	Tropical Moist forests	25 (1-ha)	[Zuleta <i>et al.</i> , 2017]: Amacayacu forest dynamics plot (AFDP)
Colombia	Tropical moist forests, montane forests	134 (0.1 ha), 16 (1.0 ha),	Alvaro Duque (Personal Communications): Alvaro Duque <ajduque09@gmail.com>
Colombia	Tropical wet forests Choco	225 (0.25 ha)	[Meyer <i>et al.</i> , 2018]
Bolivia	Inundated, liana, secondary, semi-deciduous, deciduous, evergreen	176 (0.1-0.25 ha)	[Saatchi <i>et al.</i> , 2011]
Brazil	Tropical moist, woodland, savanna	737 (0.1-5 ha)	[Saatchi <i>et al.</i> , 2011]
Brazil	Atlantic forests, tropical moist forests, cerrado	844 (0.1 ha)	[Lima <i>et al.</i> , 2011]: Southern Brazil Inventory Data
Brazil	Mixed conifer forests, Araucaria moist forests	449 (0.1 ha)	Santa Catarina Forest and Floristic Inventory (IFFSC)
Chile	Lenga and coigue forest	35 (0.1 ha)	Winrock/Wildlife Conservation Society: https://www.winrock.org
Colombia	Terra firme, inundated, agroforestry	164 (0.1 - 1 ha)	[Saatchi <i>et al.</i> , 2011]
Costa Rica	Tropical rain forest	238 (0.5 ha)	[Clark <i>et al.</i> , 2019]: David Clark <dbclark50@yahoo.com>
Ecuador	Terra firme and swamp forests	44 (0.1-1 ha)	[Pitman <i>et al.</i> , 1999]
Guyana	Moist tropical forest	28 (1 ha)	[Sanden, 1997]
Northwest South America	tropical inundated forests	34 (1.0 ha)	[Álvarez-Dávila <i>et al.</i> , 2017]
Panama	Tropical forest	50 plots (1 ha)	FORESTGeo: Stuart Davies: S Davies DaviesS@si.edu
Peru	Terra firme, floodplain forests	184 (0.1 - 1 ha)	[Saatchi <i>et al.</i> , 2011]: saatchi@jpl.nasa.gov
Africa			
Botswana	Woodland savanna	3 (1 ha)	Hank Shugart, University of Virginia: Shugart, Herman H. (Hank) (hhs) <hhs@virginia.edu>
Cameroon	forest-savanna transition	11	[Mitchard <i>et al.</i> , 2009]: Edward Mitchard <edward.mitchard@ed.ac.uk>
Central and West Africa	Old growth forests	79	[Lewis <i>et al.</i> , 2009]: Simon Lewis [GEO] <S.L.Lewis@leeds.ac.uk>

Gabon	tropical rain forest	850 (0.1 - 1 ha)	Ministry of Forest: Lee White <lwhiteanpn@gmail.com>
Guinea	various	574 (0.1 ha)	Winrock: https://www.winrock.org
Kenya	primary and secondary, mountain and sub-mountain, woodland	240 (0.04 - 1 ha)	[<i>Saatchi et al.</i> , 2011]
Madagascar	Primary and secondary	202 (0.1 - 1 ha)	[<i>Saatchi et al.</i> , 2011]
Malawi	Woodland savanna	184 (0.1 ha)	Edward Mitchard, University of Edinburgh: Edward Mitchard <edward.mitchard@ed.ac.uk>
Mozambique	Woodland savanna, mountain forests, coastal forests, Miombo woodlands	170 (0.1 - 1 ha)	[<i>Ribeiro et al.</i> , 2008]: Natasha Ribeiro: joluci2000@yahoo.com
Republic of Congo	tropical rain forest	10 (0.1 ha)	Winrock / USAID: https://www.winrock.org
Tanzania	Miombo woodlands	88 (0.07 ha)	[<i>Næsset et al.</i> , 2016]: Erik Næsset: erik.naesset@nmbu.no
DRC	Moist tropical forests, woodlands	135 (1-ha)	[<i>Xu et al.</i> , 2017]: https://wwf.panda.org/?300412/A-National-Forest-Carbon-Map-for-the-DRC
Uganda	Tropical forest-savanna transition	141 (0.5-2 ha)	Edward Mitchard, University of Edinburgh: edward.mitchard@ed.ac.uk
Republic of Congo	Tropical moist, woodland, savanna	864 (0.5 ha)	http://www.fao.org/forestry/16185-0d614ff2aad80fd21ea10c619c0a28276.pdf
Asia/Australia			
Australia	Tropical moist	25 (1 ha)	[<i>Bradford et al.</i> , 2014] Matt Bradford: Bradford, Matt (L&W, Atherton) <Matt.Bradford@csiro.au>
Indonesia	primary, peat swamp, agroforestry	58 (0.1 ha)	[<i>Saatchi et al.</i> , 2011]
Malaysia, Indonesia	tropical old growth, peat swamp	480 (0.1 - 1 ha)	Alexandra Morel, Oxford University: Alexandra Morel <alexandra.morel@gmail.com>
Philippines	tropical rain forest, undisturbed dipterocarp forest, secondary tropical rain forest	39 (0.1 - 1 ha, 250 m transect)	[<i>Saatchi et al.</i> , 2011]

Vietnam	tropical moist forest	49 (0.1 ha)	Winrock / USAID: https://www.winrock.org
Indonesia	tropical moist forest	104(0.1-0.25)	[<i>Ferraz et al.</i> , 2018]
Nepal	various broadleaf and needleleaf	216 (0.05 - 0.075 ha)	ICIMOD, Nepal: MSR Murthy: mmurthy@icimod.org

Table S2: Height-biomass allometric equations and root:shoot ratios for calculation of BGB. Equations are collected from various sources as well as developed as a part of this study. North America FIA regional models and root:shoot ratios were based on FIA plot level data. General tropical broadleaf evergreen models are from different sources (Saatchi et al., 2011; Mokany et al., 2006; Ryan et al., 2011). We used the middle value (2.5:1) between a typical range of AGB:BGB ratio of 2:1 to 3:1 in mangroves (Komiya et al., 2008).

Vegetation Type	Height to AGB Conversion	R^2	RMSE (Mg/ha)	n	Root:Shoot BGB to AGB
<i>Africa</i>					
Broadleaf Evergreen	$AGB = 0.2788H^{2.12}$	0.80		75	*0.205 0.235
Woodlands	$\dagger AGB = 0.12363H^{2.3533}$	0.86	95.5	49	$\dagger 0.42AGB$
<i>Australia</i>					
Broadleaf Evergreen	$AGB = 0.39194H^{2.1506}$	0.96	34.5	31	*0.205 0.235
<i>Eurasia</i>					
Broadleaf Deciduous (east)	$AGB = 0.26089H^{2.1192}$	0.45	84.5	60	*0.456 0.226 0.241
Boreal (east)	$AGB = 0.2H^{2.2194}$	0.39	19.1	202	*0.392 0.239
Boreal (west)	$AGB = 3.9314H^{1.2103}$	0.84	18.5	468	0.23803AGB
					1.7071 + 0.21461AGB
Mediterranean	$AGB = 1.4243H^{1.5953}$	0.71		257	*0.322
<i>North America</i>					
FIA Southern					
Conifer	$AGB = 0.396H^{2.2}$	0.63	35.6	11113	0.22371
Mixed	$AGB = 2.2721H^{1.5}$	0.65	35.6	3604	0.20844
Deciduous	$AGB = 0.2H^{2.3}$	0.61	44.6	20279	0.19621
FIA North Eastern					
Conifer	$AGB = 2.35H^{1.55}$	0.55	34.8	2804	0.22149
Mixed	$AGB = 0.3H^{2.37}$	0.58	36.8	500	0.20753
Deciduous	$AGB = 4.13H^{1.3}$	0.43	49.7	14252	0.19677
FIA North Central					
Conifer	$AGB = 0.588H^{1.8661}$	0.43	32.6	5590	0.22544
Mixed	$AGB = 0.1H^{2.65}$	0.47	32.5	944	0.20916
Deciduous	$AGB = 1.6145H^{1.5}$	0.48	36.9	22031	0.19684
FIA Interior West					
Conifer	$AGB = 3.1429H^{1.2}$	0.54	46.2	4044	0.22797
Deciduous	$AGB = 3.486H^{1.2}$	0.58	37.5	497	0.20634
FIA Pacific					
Conifer	$AGB = 2.335H^{1.3}$	0.67	99.3	4031	0.22394
Deciduous	$AGB = 5.4311H^{1.1}$	0.51	90.1	960	0.20541
Canada					
Montane Cordillera	$AGB = 1.5248H^{1.5512}$	0.65	38.3	25	*0.392 0.239
Pacific Maritime	$AGB = 3.4819H^{1.2558}$	0.80	30.2	25	*0.403 0.292 0.201
Boreal Cordillera	$AGB = 0.61335H^{1.8054}$	0.47	23.0	25	*0.392 0.239
Boreal Plains	$AGB = 2.1745H^{1.5258}$	0.81	13.5	25	*0.392 0.239
Boreal Shields	$AGB = 2.0657H^{1.5548}$	0.67	20.0	25	*0.392 0.239
Atlantic Maritime	$AGB = 0.47767H^{2.0538}$	0.51	21.1	25	*0.456 0.226 0.241
Temperate Savanna, Shrubland	$AGB = 1.3403H^{1.4694}$	0.60	32.6	3089	*0.642
Mediterranean Forests, Woodlands	$AGB = 2.3053H^{1.3171}$	0.44	49.2	322	*0.322
Tropical Dry Broadleaf	$AGB = 0.24888H^{2.4469}$	0.35	28.9	4833	*0.563 0.275
Tropical Conifer	$AGB = 4.0685H^{1.1974}$	0.40	34.5	2770	*0.563 0.275
<i>South America</i>					
Tropical Moist Forest					
General Broadleaf Evergreen	$AGB = 0.6011H^{1.894}$	0.86		298	*0.205 0.235
Southern Amazon	$AGB = 3.1721H^{1.3257}$	0.82			*0.205 0.235
Central Amazon	$AGB = 2.4673H^{1.4706}$	0.74			*0.205 0.235
Western Amazon	$AGB = 0.23065H^{2.217}$	0.79			*0.205 0.235
Northeastern Amazon	$AGB = 0.2163H^{2.1835}$	0.45	59.7	33	*0.205 0.235
Colombia	$AGB = 0.00945H^{3.18566}$	0.63	16.4	25	*0.205 0.235
Eastern Coastal	$AGB = 0.95843H^{1.8102}$	0.79			*0.205 0.235
<i>Southeast Asia</i>					
Broadleaf Evergreen	$AGB = 0.21608H^{2.1604}$	0.58		303	0.489AGB ^{0.89}
Mangrove	$AGB = 0.7067H^{1.7862}$	0.61	102.8	11	$\ddagger 0.4$

Table S3. Distribution of forest and nonforest area and carbon storage for countries globally.

Country	Forest			Non-Forest		
	(Million hectare)	Carbon (Tg)		(Million hectare)	Carbon (Tg)	
	Area	AGB	BGB	Area	AGB	BGB
Afghanistan	1.942	55.59	14.42	22.63	201.4	48.99
Aland	0.0567	2.379	0.5690	0.0075	0.0682	0.0163
Albania	1.662	34.36	7.632	1.063	10.02	2.187
Algeria	2.019	73.61	18.23	15.52	125.0	28.88
Andorra	0.0258	1.015	0.2306	0.0182	0.4117	0.0922
Angola	60.76	2514	710.5	61.80	741.8	255.6
Anguilla	0.0036	0.1090	0.0252	0.0007	0.0166	0.0036
Antigua and Barbuda	0.0223	1.156	0.2594	0.0126	0.3921	0.0819
Argentina	14.34	537.9	118.2	200.3	1603	398.4
Armenia	0.5350	12.69	2.835	2.388	17.32	3.754
Australia	146.4	4576	1125	436.9	1978	469.6
Austria	5.191	242.7	53.04	2.976	58.52	12.91
Azerbaijan	1.722	48.01	10.44	6.276	60.90	13.65
Bahrain	0.0010	0.0270	0.0054	0.0142	0.1900	0.0396
Bangladesh	2.444	104.9	30.88	9.812	104.6	41.79
Barbados	0.0162	0.7895	0.1796	0.0189	0.4035	0.0875
Belarus	11.00	394.1	85.66	9.528	76.70	15.70
Belgium	1.664	46.72	9.956	1.344	11.72	2.473
Belize	1.842	139.8	32.14	0.3438	6.567	1.500
Benin	5.064	170.6	68.04	6.525	100.9	30.75
Bhutan	2.527	133.1	30.55	1.044	35.32	8.250
Bolivia	59.17	3770	860.2	37.53	463.6	114.2
Bosnia and Herzegovina	3.986	117.7	26.67	1.160	12.25	2.601
Botswana	1.214	30.78	9.456	51.97	230.3	53.10
Brazil	433.1	38985	9182	397.6	7011	1738
British Virgin Islands	0.0052	0.4658	0.1087	0.0010	0.0652	0.0152
Brunei	0.4764	56.85	13.80	0.0722	2.532	0.7306
Bulgaria	5.717	146.7	31.37	5.437	46.60	9.889
Burkina Faso	3.729	103.4	31.75	22.56	216.9	51.60
Burundi	1.079	35.41	10.81	1.402	26.54	9.911
Cambodia	8.343	524.3	139.0	9.038	192.1	56.62
Cameroon	38.05	2967	835.4	7.802	105.9	33.31
Canada	464.2	17056	4456	388.8	6880	1656
Cayman Islands	0.0117	0.2726	0.0629	0.0033	0.0655	0.0149
Central African Republic	57.40	3237	1221	4.626	75.83	28.72
Chad	11.43	349.0	128.0	38.56	334.4	94.26
Chile	14.63	678.0	164.4	32.27	510.7	135.7
China	226.1	10439	2771	442.8	7465	1952
Colombia	71.46	6361	1486	40.05	879.9	200.2
Comoros	0.1089	5.742	1.288	0.0257	0.5793	0.1265
Costa Rica	4.586	325.8	75.23	0.4229	15.14	3.420
Croatia	3.789	109.5	24.90	1.544	17.20	3.627
Cuba	6.630	359.0	87.47	3.793	112.0	26.09

Country	Forest			Non-Forest		
	(Million hectare)	Carbon (Tg)		(Million hectare)	Carbon (Tg)	
	Area	AGB	BGB	Area	AGB	BGB
Cyprus	0.1422	4.268	1.080	0.3522	3.656	0.8844
Czech Republic	4.152	196.0	42.35	3.656	23.62	4.931
Democratic Republic of the Congo	180.6	17944	4303	49.27	682.6	205.9
Denmark	1.204	27.33	5.782	2.676	14.73	3.008
Djibouti	0.0011	0.0314	0.0084	0.6488	5.459	1.302
Dominica	0.0599	5.940	1.542	0.0014	0.1149	0.0282
Dominican Republic	3.394	177.6	39.65	1.268	42.80	8.988
East Timor	0.8064	58.10	14.47	0.6368	24.44	6.436
Ecuador	16.52	1291	304.0	8.100	226.0	53.42
Egypt	0.1229	2.739	0.7198	1.794	14.16	3.506
El Salvador	1.796	117.3	30.73	0.2041	8.103	2.029
Equatorial Guinea	2.599	305.5	70.94	0.0279	1.628	0.3723
Eritrea	1.107	37.79	9.962	5.637	72.90	19.25
Estonia	3.085	101.6	21.54	1.155	5.151	1.072
Ethiopia	43.77	1707	496.1	58.56	884.8	232.9
Falkland Islands	0.0049	0.1335	0.0416	0.9722	4.610	1.102
Fiji	1.062	86.69	20.25	0.3886	14.88	3.556
Finland	24.04	941.8	208.1	6.696	79.18	17.95
France	34.92	1832	416.0	27.75	210.1	43.92
Gabon	24.25	3126	732.2	1.525	12.08	3.056
Gambia	0.2253	5.861	1.592	0.7399	8.544	1.985
Georgia	3.845	96.12	21.35	3.000	35.04	7.769
Germany	18.30	686.1	147.5	16.72	124.0	26.26
Ghana	9.526	463.0	122.0	13.56	198.0	72.90
Greece	7.551	273.4	62.85	4.583	53.98	11.93
Grenada	0.0065	0.5669	0.1306	0.0192	1.371	0.3134
Guam	0.0000	0.0009	0.0003	0.0000	0.0005	0.0001
Guatemala	8.995	523.5	125.4	1.663	53.84	13.26
Guernsey	0.0017	0.0331	0.0076	0.0023	0.0291	0.0068
Guinea Bissau	2.618	91.67	29.02	0.4833	5.560	1.562
Guinea	20.12	852.8	310.4	4.193	74.75	25.77
Guyana	18.80	2179	507.9	1.969	25.76	6.408
Haiti	1.616	81.62	18.40	0.9400	33.11	7.006
Honduras	9.528	583.9	135.4	1.498	48.96	11.70
Hong Kong S.A.R.	0.0541	3.480	0.8950	0.0210	0.5712	0.1715
Hungary	3.398	72.05	15.43	5.809	44.10	9.336
Iceland	0.3939	4.571	1.250	6.878	25.80	6.298
India	58.94	2900	827.5	238.6	3086	843.7
Indonesia	115.5	12925	3132	65.34	2442	709.9
Iran	7.486	263.8	66.68	42.99	316.9	78.91
Iraq	0.8853	27.87	7.060	9.685	49.91	11.41
Ireland	1.806	31.52	8.723	4.846	21.09	4.794
Isle of Man	0.0137	0.3333	0.0954	0.0389	0.2402	0.0590
Israel	0.3310	10.88	2.628	0.7173	6.704	1.484

Country	Forest			Non-Forest		
	(Million hectare)	Carbon (Tg)		(Million hectare)	Carbon (Tg)	
	Area	AGB	BGB	Area	AGB	BGB
Italy	14.69	388.6	83.67	14.34	163.0	35.02
Ivory Coast	26.64	1190	371.0	5.384	101.4	35.57
Jamaica	0.9366	73.83	16.98	0.1133	4.192	0.9318
Japan	28.47	2139	538.9	6.770	99.70	32.77
Jersey	0.0052	0.0832	0.0190	0.0051	0.0463	0.0100
Jordan	0.1079	3.458	0.8712	0.8189	7.222	1.893
Kazakhstan	4.402	150.0	42.64	172.4	2623	638.7
Kenya	14.15	531.3	150.0	35.47	476.1	121.4
Kuwait	0.0069	0.1272	0.0256	0.0415	0.4187	0.0849
Kyrgyzstan	0.9677	24.63	7.073	11.52	68.20	19.05
Laos	19.11	1297	341.3	3.670	131.5	37.22
Latvia	4.248	144.3	30.93	2.051	10.27	2.154
Lebanon	0.5099	17.83	4.241	0.4338	5.739	1.350
Lesotho	0.0089	0.1922	0.0718	2.790	14.75	4.611
Liberia	9.437	845.8	193.6	0.0767	1.644	0.3665
Libya	0.1158	3.322	0.9654	1.991	13.14	3.271
Liechtenstein	0.0060	0.1799	0.0403	0.0081	0.2233	0.0499
Lithuania	2.910	100.5	21.59	3.450	16.93	3.470
Luxembourg	0.1528	5.037	1.054	0.1071	0.6907	0.1446
Macao S.A.R	0.0006	0.0517	0.0126	0.0009	0.0119	0.0030
Macedonia	1.609	37.83	8.137	0.8734	9.227	2.049
Madagascar	16.26	733.5	167.5	39.92	343.9	90.84
Malawi	2.356	94.65	27.46	7.139	83.84	26.14
Malaysia	22.06	2796	678.8	10.06	454.1	130.0
Mali	8.752	267.2	87.85	37.15	289.9	73.34
Malta	0.0037	0.1112	0.0267	0.0164	0.2735	0.0602
Mauritania	0.0880	2.962	0.8434	10.69	30.69	7.496
Mauritius	0.1137	4.896	1.090	0.0527	0.9604	0.2097
Mexico	96.68	3649	970.7	93.31	1415	407.8
Moldova	0.5640	11.76	2.599	2.732	29.22	6.252
Monaco	0.0010	0.0382	0.0087	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
Mongolia	12.59	367.0	105.6	57.83	550.1	140.5
Montenegro	1.052	32.04	7.147	0.2841	3.664	0.7894
Montserrat	0.0047	0.4112	0.0961	0.0020	0.0699	0.0167
Morocco	1.958	59.77	15.58	17.44	156.2	37.44
Mozambique	39.56	1552	461.8	36.79	597.5	186.9
Myanmar	42.52	3395	885.1	22.03	419.5	120.0
Namibia	5.011	130.1	40.02	59.96	294.5	79.02
Nepal	6.743	274.1	76.08	6.667	127.9	35.13
Netherlands	1.213	24.30	5.261	1.982	12.40	2.726
New Caledonia	0.9331	75.64	17.86	0.8062	40.90	9.976
New Zealand	14.95	1072	275.4	9.675	121.9	31.52
Nicaragua	9.948	668.4	156.1	1.848	47.67	11.24
Niger	0.2924	8.504	2.686	24.33	69.52	16.93
Nigeria	29.95	1360	473.3	57.68	707.3	197.9

Country	Forest			Non-Forest		
	(Million hectare)	Carbon (Tg)		(Million hectare)	Carbon (Tg)	
	Area	AGB	BGB	Area	AGB	BGB
North Korea	7.719	434.7	111.1	3.690	83.44	23.40
Northern Mariana Islands	0.0001	0.0031	0.0012	0.0009	0.0401	0.0116
Norway	13.88	522.9	118.5	13.93	122.5	27.19
Oman	0.2030	6.853	2.177	0.4773	4.254	1.240
Pakistan	2.766	74.12	19.66	39.34	539.6	134.0
Palau	0.0224	2.470	0.5973	0.0053	0.3054	0.0815
Palestine	0.2136	6.982	1.723	0.2944	3.581	0.8768
Panama	6.555	501.8	116.5	0.5833	14.36	3.171
Papua New Guinea	33.80	3756	894.8	11.46	669.6	169.6
Paraguay	12.20	477.1	100.3	26.89	457.8	100.8
Peru	73.71	6995	1642	41.15	768.8	197.0
Philippines	9.206	1029	248.5	18.19	883.4	248.1
Poland	13.79	541.9	118.6	17.10	96.71	19.91
Portugal	3.329	76.59	18.52	5.229	53.27	12.55
Puerto Rico	0.7446	54.84	12.64	0.1016	3.388	0.7590
Qatar	0.0028	0.0688	0.0145	0.0302	0.4072	0.0837
Republic of Congo	26.01	2687	633.1	8.409	76.96	20.45
Republic of Serbia	4.304	100.1	22.47	3.388	28.52	5.996
Romania	9.786	275.3	60.79	13.52	116.4	24.57
Russia	839.3	34153	8885	730.1	8121	2180
Rwanda	0.7177	27.63	7.103	1.657	33.18	8.926
Saint Barthelemy	0.0010	0.1228	0.0270	0.0005	0.0490	0.0108
Saint Kitts and Nevis	0.0172	1.454	0.3310	0.0024	0.1269	0.0277
Saint Lucia	0.0502	5.485	1.309	0.0013	0.0577	0.0129
Saint Martin	0.0031	0.2708	0.0657	0.0004	0.0148	0.0035
Saint Pierre and Miquelon	0.0076	0.3843	0.0820	0.0085	0.1688	0.0384
Saint Vincent and the Grenadines	0.0269	2.302	0.5324	0.0022	0.1404	0.0318
San Marino	0.0041	0.0709	0.0170	0.0023	0.0203	0.0044
Sao Tome and Principe	0.0318	0.5829	0.1223	0.0040	0.0363	0.0075
Saudi Arabia	0.7143	24.91	7.606	2.269	34.08	10.13
Senegal	4.355	138.6	50.63	12.99	94.94	23.96
Seychelles	0.0003	0.0160	0.0036	0.0009	0.0453	0.0100
Sierra Leone	6.418	331.2	88.90	0.6893	13.31	3.715
Singapore	0.0175	0.5595	0.1515	0.0261	0.3970	0.1028
Sint Maarten	0.0019	0.1706	0.0415	0.0005	0.0264	0.0063
Slovakia	3.028	108.0	23.77	1.788	15.76	3.364
Slovenia	1.500	58.26	12.42	0.5131	15.09	3.267
Solomon Islands	2.127	276.6	66.13	0.2268	21.56	5.299
Somalia	11.56	431.7	121.7	32.13	419.7	107.4
South Africa	10.25	341.6	106.9	81.79	487.0	146.3
South Korea	7.591	594.8	150.1	1.706	50.30	14.46
South Sudan	24.37	913.9	357.6	33.66	367.1	122.1
Spain	16.19	462.9	112.9	32.11	267.6	61.80
Sri Lanka	3.577	215.9	57.13	2.816	82.39	23.97
Sudan	7.507	243.4	74.69	53.77	394.8	102.1

Country	Forest			Non-Forest		
	(Million hectare)	Carbon (Tg)		(Million hectare)	Carbon (Tg)	
	Area	AGB	BGB	Area	AGB	BGB
Suriname	13.56	1682	393.6	0.7316	22.33	4.970
Swaziland	0.6207	21.19	7.298	1.042	11.74	3.924
Sweden	32.50	1368	305.2	8.661	77.29	17.18
Switzerland	1.938	59.45	13.20	1.730	29.79	6.644
Syria	0.5966	22.13	5.193	5.712	33.65	8.050
Tajikistan	0.6611	20.12	4.857	6.617	75.19	17.39
Thailand	23.64	1575	422.0	26.80	468.6	130.6
The Bahamas	0.5442	14.84	3.699	0.3411	5.376	1.349
Togo	2.029	79.62	31.61	3.625	47.42	15.67
Trinidad and Tobago	0.3581	32.32	7.864	0.1257	5.205	1.243
Tunisia	0.4624	19.26	4.353	5.537	36.51	8.129
Turkey	24.24	759.1	183.1	48.44	424.4	96.09
Turkmenistan	0.0430	1.014	0.2227	4.731	18.22	3.693
Turks and Caicos Islands	0.0161	0.4388	0.1051	0.0070	0.1256	0.0295
Uganda	4.903	208.0	53.13	15.52	269.6	68.09
Ukraine	13.42	409.1	89.57	44.87	447.7	95.76
United Arab Emirates	0.0137	0.2745	0.0597	0.0677	0.8546	0.1967
United Kingdom	6.588	164.9	45.60	16.70	102.4	24.71
United Republic of Tanzania	39.79	1514	434.9	46.49	575.3	160.1
United States Virgin Islands	0.0217	1.984	0.4606	0.0050	0.2586	0.0555
United States of America	372.2	21510	4970	528.2	10183	3178
Uruguay	0.7914	24.99	6.537	14.59	118.1	26.02
Uzbekistan	0.6342	14.70	3.518	11.45	69.80	15.51
Vanuatu	0.6301	41.82	9.328	0.3787	23.46	5.228
Venezuela	51.41	4120	955.7	37.28	754.4	175.7
Vietnam	16.41	1133	298.2	14.17	410.4	119.0
Yemen	1.338	43.24	13.48	3.197	48.51	14.53
Zambia	37.81	1385	464.4	35.41	422.9	149.0
Zimbabwe	10.82	328.0	105.3	27.21	276.2	73.40
Total	4593	262426	65892	5770	78491	20984
		328.3 PgC			99.47 PgC	